

Cryptic Diversity in Toads of the *Rhinella marina* species group (Anura, Bufonidae) with a subjectively beautiful new species from Western Ecuador

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ABSTRACT

The mainly Mesoamerican Cane Toad, *Rhinella horribilis*, is the northernmost species in the *R. marina* species group of Giant or Cane Toads, occupying an extensive range west of the Andean Cordillera from Ecuador north to southern Texas. However, a thorough assessment of geographic variation among *R. horribilis* populations, and of the phylogenetic relationships of the *R. marina* species complex, indicates previously unsuspected diversity within this species as, currently recognized. Specifically, we evaluated whether toad populations from western Ecuador represent an evolutionary lineage distinct from the rest of *R. horribilis* based on extensive specimen collections and the combined evidence of mtDNA sequence variation, morphological, bioacoustics and environmental information. Our results revealed that populations west of the Ecuadorian Andes constitute a well-supported, monophyletic clade that is distinctly different genetically, morphologically, acoustically and ecologically from a sister taxon composed of *R. horribilis* populations from Central America and from populations ascribable to *R. marina sensu*

stricto from the Amazon Basin of Ecuador and other countries. The weight of evidence confirms a new species, described here, adding to our understanding of biogeographic relationships in this widespread clade of Neotropical toads. The new species name means "beautiful" in Latin, in contrast to its sister species, "*horribilis*".

Keywords: Amphibians; bella, bioacoustics; divergence; geometric morphometrics; morphology; phylogeny; *Rhinella marina*; species delineation; systematics

INTRODUCTION

Rhinella marina, the Cane Toad, has a long and complex taxonomic history. Once considered to be a single, widely distributed, neotropical species in the large and cosmopolitan genus, *Bufo*, *R. marina* is currently considered to be one of the 10 species in the *R. marina* species group (Martin, 1972; Pereyra *et al.*, 2021). This group occurs natively in the Americas from as far north as southern Texas in the United States to as far south as Uruguay in South America (Blair, 1972; Cei, 1972; Pauly *et al.*, 2004; Maciel *et al.*, 2010). Nine of these species – *R. achavali*, *R. arenarum*, *R. cerradensis*, *R. icterica*, *R. diptycha*, *R. marina*, *R. poeppigii*, *R. rubescens*, and *R. veredas* – are naturally confined to South America, where the group most probably originated (Pauly *et al.*, 2004; Pramuk, 2006; Pramuk *et al.*, 2008; Maciel *et al.*, 2010; Vallinoto *et al.*, 2010). The remaining species, *R. horribilis* occurs west of the Andean Cordillera and north through Central America and Mexico as far as southern Texas. The monophyly of this species group is supported by morphological, molecular, and skin-secretion evidence (Pramuk, 2006; Maciel *et al.*, 2010). Two putative morphological synapomorphies are: a) The presence of a jagged or scalloped articulation between the medial ramus of pterygoid and parasphenoid alae

and b) The presence of a sacral diapophyses with the anterior edge angled posteriorly to the midline axis of the vertebral column (Pramuk, 2006; Pereyra *et al.*, 2021).

Rhinella marina was described by Linnaeus (1758), who listed its type locality as “America”, although the type specimen was probably collected in Suriname (Müller & Hellmich, 1936). It is widely distributed in the Guianan region and the Amazon Basin, with introduced populations in the United States, Australia, Japan, Philippines, Taiwan, Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands and many Caribbean and Pacific islands (Easteal, 1981, 1985; Lever, 2001; Shine, 2010; Acevedo *et al.*, 2016; Frost, 2020). The taxonomy of *R. marina* has many problems in need of resolution, including the evidence of paraphyly reported by Vallinoto *et al.* (2010) and Slade & Moritz (1998).

Acevedo *et al.* (2016) proposed that populations of *Rhinella marina* west of the Andes in South America, Central America/Mexico, and southern Texas comprise a distinct species, based on mitochondrial DNA and morphometric data, for which the name *R. horribilis* (Wiegmann 1833; type locality Veracruz, México) is applicable. This taxonomic change, suggested mainly by comparisons between Venezuelan populations of *R. horribilis* and *R. marina*, has been recently supported by Bessa-Silva *et al.* (2020) based on both mitochondrial DNA and nuclear data. However, it is likely that *R. horribilis*, as currently defined, includes more than one species. This scenario was suggested by Vallinoto *et al.* (2010), who found evidence of two, allopatric, mitochondrial DNA clades within “*R. horribilis*”: one in Central America and the other in western Ecuador. Additional evidence of the existence of more than one species is provided by an estimate of 10.9 My for the divergence between Central America populations and one sample from Western Ecuador (Mulcahy *et al.*, 2006). More recently, Pereyra *et al.* (2021) reported a deep incongruence in the phylogenetic position of *R. horribilis sensu lato* when comparing

mitochondrial and nuclear DNA. This incongruence was hypothesized to be the result of ancient mitochondrial introgression into *R. horribilis* from an unknown species of *Rhinella*. Pereyra *et al.* (2021) proposed that the populations of the *R. marina* group from western Ecuador represent an undescribed species based on the deep genetic divergence between populations from Central America (*R. horribilis sensu stricto*) and western Ecuador. This genetic evidence needs to be reconciled with phenotypic characters to determine the taxonomic status of populations of the *R. marina* group from western Ecuador.

In this study, we evaluate the phylogenetic relationships of populations of the *R. marina* group with emphasis on Ecuadorian populations based on mitochondrial DNA, morphological, bioacoustic and ecological characters. Our sampling includes extensive new collections of specimens from Central America and Mexico (hereafter referred to as only Central America) and both the Pacific and Amazonian basins of Ecuador. If the populations west of the Ecuadorian Andes (Pacific basin) are taxonomically discrete to the extent that they are an independent evolutionary lineage, they should comprise a monophyletic clade to the exclusion of other such populations and possess differences in acoustic, morphological, and/or environmental niche characters. Our results indicate that the populations from western Ecuador do represent a new species, which we describe here.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Molecular phylogenetics

To resolve phylogenetic relationships among *Rhinella marina* species group toads, we combined published and new sequences of the mitochondrial genes 12S rRNA, tRNA-Val, and 16S rRNA. We obtained sequences from 55 specimens from GenBank, representing eight species of the *R. marina* species group: *R. achavali*, *R. arenarum*, *R. diptycha*, *R. horribilis*, *R.*

icterica, *R. marina*, *R. poeppigii*, and *R. rubescens*. We also included seven species of New World toads as outgroups: *R. crucifer*, *R. granulosa*, *Anaxyrus exsul*, *A. fowleri*, *A. microscaphus*, *Incilius alvarius* and *I. valliceps*. Published sequences for *R. marina sensu lato* included samples from the eastern Andes and Amazonia, as well from western Ecuador. Sequences of *R. horribilis* from Central America were available in GenBank only for the 16S gene. We extended this dataset by generating 68 new sequences for the 12S, tRNA-Val and 16S genes from specimens of *R. marina* species group collected on both the eastern and western sides of the Ecuadorian Andes (Fig. 1, Supporting information, Table S1). We assembled and aligned DNA sequences with Geneious Pro 5.5 (Drummond *et al.*, 2011) using the GENEIOUS alignment algorithm, and used PartitionFinder v1.1.1 (Lanfear *et al.* 2012) to select the best-fit nucleotide substitution models, and the best partitioning scheme for our data matrix of 2476 bp.

We used both Bayesian and Maximum likelihood methods to estimate phylogenetic relationships. We performed four independent Bayesian analyses using MrBayes 3.2 (Ronquist *et al.*, 2012). For each one, we ran 10^6 generations and four Markov chains with default heating values, sampling trees every 1000 generations. We used Tracer 1.6 (Rambaut *et al.*, 2013) to examine stationarity, posterior estimates, and effective sample size (ESS) for model parameters. After confirming convergence of the results from the four independent searches, we discarded the initial 10% of the generations as burn-in and the remaining generations were used to estimate a 50% majority rule consensus tree and the posterior probabilities for each node. We performed Maximum likelihood analysis using PhyML (Guindon & Gascuel, 2003) with a subtree pruning and regrafting (SPR) topology search. We estimated node support based on 500 bootstrap replicates. In addition, we used MEGA 5 (Tamura *et al.*, 2011) to estimate pairwise uncorrected (*p*) genetic distances among mitochondrial clades using partial sequences of the 16S gene (ca.

520 pb). To visualize the observed genetic distances, we performed a multidimensional scaling (MDS) plot of the pairwise distance matrix using the *cmdscale* function in program R (R Development Core Team 2017).

Acoustic analysis of calls

Recordings of advertisement calls were obtained from various sources: ten recordings from the audio archive of QCAZ, four from Museo Gustavo Orcés at Escuela Politécnica Nacional (MEPN), one from the audio CD “Frogs of Tambopata” (Cocroft *et al.*, 2001). Three recordings were downloaded from FonoZoo (<http://www.fonozoo.com>), and four recordings from Macaulay Library at the Cornell Lab of Ornithology (<https://www.macaulaylibrary.org>). A total of 157 calls from 35 individuals were analyzed (Supporting Information, Table S2): 17 individuals from western Ecuador, 13 from eastern side of the Andes and Amazonia (i.e. 12 from eastern Ecuador and one from eastern Peru), and five from Central America (i.e. of *R. horribilis*).

We digitized calls using Raven Pro 1.6.4 software (<https://ravensoundsoftware.com>) at a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz with 16-bit accuracy. The spectrogram analyses used settings of window type Hann, window size 890 samples and filter bandwidth 71.3 Hz, and a frequency resolution of 44.1 Hz. When available, several calls or notes were analyzed per individual to calculate an individual average. Temporal variables were measured on the oscillogram, spectral variables on the power spectrum. Acoustic variables and terminology of calls were adapted from Duellman & Trueb (1986), and are as follows: (1) call length (time between onset of first pulse and offset of last pulse in a call); (2) call rise time (time required for a call to reach its maximum amplitude); (3) notes per call (number of notes); (4) pulses per note (number of pulses); (5) pulse rate (number of pulses repeated in a defined period of time within a note); (6) call repetition rate

(number of calls/min); and (7) dominant frequency (frequency with the most energy, measured along all the call). We used these variables to run a PCA to assess the degree of acoustic variation among populations of *R. horribilis* from Central America (two males from Costa Rica, three males from Mexico), western Ecuador (six males from Mindo, one male from Puyango, one male from Río Baba, two males from Yunguilla, four males from Río Palenque, three males from Zapotillo), and eastern Ecuador and Peru (three males from Cordillera del Cóndor [Campamento Las Peñas, next to the Machinaza river], one male from Montalvo, six males from Puerto Morona, two males from Via Maxus, and one male from Tambopata-Peru). We then used the informative principal components (PCs) for a MANOVA, followed by post hoc multiple comparison analyses using the Bonferroni corrected approach (Rice, 1989).

Ambient temperature data were not provided for approximately half of the analyzed vocalizations, which precluded accurate estimation of an effect of temperature on the structure of calls (Gerhardt & Huber, 2002; Köhler *et al.*, 2017). While we acknowledge this limitation, our available data show low variation in recording temperature among populations (i.e. < 6.5 C degrees), suggesting that temperature likely may not explain the interpopulation call differences observed in our study (Caminer & Ron, 2014). Moreover, given the weak temperature dependence of dominant frequency in calls of anurans (Köhler *et al.*, 2017), we performed Mann–Whitney univariate tests to assess differences only in this call trait among toad populations.

Morphometric analysis

To assess the degree of morphometric variation and differentiation among Central American, Amazonian and western Ecuadorian *R. marina* populations, we used both linear and

geometric morphometric techniques. To reduce the noise due to developmental variability, we only analyzed adult individuals. We determined sexual maturity of males by the presence of vocal slits, and/or nuptial excrescences, and by inspection of gonadal development. Sexual maturity of females was assessed by the presence of pigmented eggs and convoluted oviducts.

Linear morphological measurements were taken with digital calipers to the nearest 0.01 mm from a total of 106 individuals: 20 from Central America (i.e. *R. horribilis*), 26 from the eastern side of the Ecuadorian Andes, and 60 from the western side of the Ecuadorian Andes (Supporting information, Table S3). We used only well-preserved specimens fixed in 10% formalin and preserved in 70% ethanol (Simmons, 2002) and, following Duellman & Schulte (1992), Lynch & Duellman (1997) and Duellman (2001), made the following measurements: snout-vent length (SVL), tibia length (TL), foot length (FL), femur length (FEL), head length (HL), head width (HW), interorbital distance (IOD), internarial distance (IND), eye-nostril distance (END), eye diameter (ED), tympanum diameter (TD), thumb length (THL), third finger length (TF). We verified normal distribution of residuals from a linear regression of all measurements against SVL using Shapiro–Wilk tests (Sokal & Rohlf, 1995), and then transformed the variables to natural logarithms to improve properties of normality. The homogeneity of the residuals was tested using a visual check of the plots of the model residuals against their fitted values (Quinn & Keough, 2002).

We used geometric morphometric analysis (Zelditch *et al.*, 2012) to assess variation attributable exclusively to shape, and focused only on the morphology of the skull, which can be related to a variety of functions (e.g. acquiring food, protecting the brain) and/or to sexual dimorphism (Birch, 1999). For this analysis we used a total of 84 specimens: 12 from Central America, 20 from the eastern side of the Ecuadorian Andes, and 52 from the western side of the

Ecuadorian Andes. We took digital X-ray radiographs in the dorsal perspective of the head of each toad with a KUBTEC XPERT 80- L Cabinet X-ray System (Milford, CT, USA) and a Thermo Kevex X-ray Imaging System. To capture the shape of the skulls, following Birch (1999), we digitized a suite of 13 fixed landmarks on the right side of each specimen from each image (Supporting information, Fig. S1) using tpsDig software (Rohlf, 2006), after setting a 1 cm scale factor; available from <https://www.sbmorphometrics.org>. We then used tpsRelW (Rohlf, 2007; available from <https://www.sbmorphometrics.org>) to perform a Generalized Procrustes Analysis (GPA) to superimpose and align landmarks (Rohlf & Slice, 1990) and quantify geometric shape variables (Kendall, 1984, 1985; Bookstein, 1991). Partial warps (i.e. geometric shape variables) themselves cannot be treated as biologically/functionally independent variables and should not be interpreted in isolation (but see for example Zelditch & Fink, 1995 or Burke *et al.*, 1996), instead, they must be interpreted all together as a joint multivariate distribution to describe the deformation of skull shape relative to the reference form, for example along canonical variate axes (Rohlf, 1998; Adrain *et al.*, 2001). Furthermore, partial warp scores can be used in statistical tests without adjusting the degrees of freedom (Zelditch *et al.*, 2012). We examined the degree of morphometric variation and divergence among populations through use of principal component analysis (PCA) and canonical variate analysis (CVA), performing separate analyses for linear and geometric morphometric variables. To remove the effect of body size, the PCA was applied to the residuals of the linear regressions between the SVL and the linear morphometric variables. We conducted a varimax rotation of the loading matrix after PCA in order to have more interpretable factors with a simpler structure than can be obtained using orthogonal rotation. We used rotated principal components scores to evaluate pairwise differences between population samples by performing the Holm-Bonferroni post-hoc correction

for multiple comparison tests (Rice, 1989). Multivariate analyses of shape variables were performed on partial warps and uniform component scores, which were extracted from the Generalized Procrustes Analyses to obtain relative warps in the case of PCA, or canonical variables in the case of CVA (Rohlf, 1993).

We acknowledge some of the criticisms of using CVA and discriminant function analysis in systematics, regarding their requirement for *a priori* definition of groups (e.g. Albrecht, 1992). However, group membership in our CVA is geographically based, and therefore there is no uncertainty about the identity of the groups. Our data showed heterogeneity across the within-group variance-covariance matrix (*Box's M* = 376.40, $P < 0.01$), therefore CVA was implemented using quadratic functions for discriminating among populations instead of linear ones (Quinn & Keough, 2002). Statistical analyses were implemented in R (R Development Core Team 2017), SPSS v. 20.0 (IBM Corp, 2011) and MorphoJ v. 1.06a (Klingenberg, 2011).

Climatic envelope analysis

Species climatic envelopes, inferred through climatic characteristics at sites of species occurrence, have been used to improve inferences about species boundaries in cryptic species (e.g. Rissler & Apodaca, 2007; Florio *et al.*, 2012; Páez-Rosales & Ron, 2019). To evaluate climatic differences among Central American, western Ecuadorian and eastern Ecuadorian populations, we only selected collection localities of the specimens used for the phylogenetic analysis ($n = 98$; see Molecular phylogenetics section and Supporting information, Table S1). We extracted values for 19 bioclimatic variables obtained from WorldClim 2.0 database (Fick & Hijmans, 2017, <https://www.worldclim.org/data/worldclim21.html>) at 30 arc-second resolution. This climatic database is generated through interpolation of average monthly temperature and

precipitation values and represent biologically meaningful variables for describing species ranges (Nix 1986). We conducted a principal component analysis (PCA) to examine the degree of climatic variation among populations. We then performed a MANOVA using informative rotated principal components (PCs), followed by post hoc multiple comparison analyses with Holm-Bonferroni correction (Rice, 1989) to evaluate pairwise differences between population samples.

RESULTS

Molecular phylogenetic analysis

Nearly identical phylogenies were obtained using Bayesian vs. Maximum Likelihood methods (Fig. 2). Both phylogenies placed, with weak support, *R. horribilis sensu lato* as sister to *R. crucifer* (Fig. 2), a result consistent with the ML phylogeny by Pereyra *et al.* (2021). Samples from Central America constituted a well-supported, monophyletic clade (Clade A in Figure 2); its sister clade also has strong support and is composed by samples from western Ecuador (Clade B = *R. sp. nov.*). Although evidence from nuclear genes indicate that the placement of this clade in the mitochondrial gene tree is an artifact of ghost introgression (Pereyra *et al.*, 2021), the divergence between Clades A and B took place after that event and, therefore, should be reliable evidence of a deep divergence between both clades. Species of the *R. marina* group east of the Andes did not assort into distinct, monophyletic clades. One clade (Clade C) consisted of samples referable to *R. arenarum*, *R. achavali*, *R. icterica* and *R. rubescens* from Uruguay, Argentina and eastern Brazil, and another clade (Clade D) was composed of *R. poeppigii* and *R. marina* samples from east of the Ecuadorian and Peruvian Andes (but see Discussion section). Clade E contained samples of *R. diptycha*, *R. poeppigii*, and *R. marina* from Argentina, Paraguay, Brazil, Surinam and eastern Ecuador (but see Discussion

section). The only monophyletic species found east of the Andes was *R. arenarum*, which formed a well-supported clade closely related to samples of *R. achavali*, *R. icterica*, and *R. rubescens* in Clade C (Fig. 2). *Rhinella marina sensu lato* was widely paraphyletic. Phylogenetic relationships were estimated for the non-partitioned 12S + tRNA-Val + 16S data set, using a GTR+ I + G model of evolution.

A phylogeny based exclusively on nuclear DNA sequences from Pereyra *et al.* (2021), lacks resolution among species of the *R. marina* complex and, therefore, is equivocal to define species limits among them (Supporting information, Fig. S5). For the same reason, it does not contradict the deep divergence between *R. horribilis* and the new species.

Uncorrected p-genetic distance between samples from western Ecuador (clade B) and samples from Central America (clade A) averaged 5.0% (Table 1; Fig. 3). This distance is higher than the distances between Clade B (*R. sp. nov.*) and all other species in the *R. marina* species group (i.e. Clades C, D and E; Table 1; Fig. 2, 3) which ranged between 4.3% – 4.8%. This distance is also much higher than the distance of 0.4% – 0.9% found among all other currently recognized species of *R. marina* group (*R. achavali*, *R. arenarum*, *R. icterica*, *R. rubescens*; Table 1), and even higher than the 3.4% – 4.3% found between *R. crucifer* and all taxa/clades of the group (Table 1).

Bioacoustic analyses

Bioacoustic comparisons indicate significant differences (see PCA results below) in call structure between western Ecuador and both *R. horribilis* and the eastern Ecuadorian clade. Calls from western Ecuador were shorter, with fewer notes, and had shorter rise time than calls from eastern Ecuador (*R. marina*) and *R. horribilis* (Table 2, 3; Fig. 4, 5). Results from Mann–

Whitney tests indicated that western Ecuadorian populations differed significantly in dominant frequency from both *R. horribilis* ($P < 0.001$) and eastern Ecuadorian populations ($P < 0.05$). Western Ecuadorian toads tended to have higher dominant frequency than Central American and eastern Ecuadorian populations (Table 3; Fig. 6).

Our PCA of advertisement calls from 35 males resulted in two PCs with eigenvalues > 1.0 (Fig. 4). These two PCs accounted for 80.06% of the total variation. PC I (60.32% of the variance) had high loadings on notes per call, call length, call rise time and dominant frequency; PC II (20.71% of the variance) had high loadings on pulse rate and pulses per note (Table 2). The acoustic space (as represented by PC I and PC II; Fig. 4) showed significant differences between western Ecuador and both Central America, and eastern Ecuador clades as determined by Pillai's trace test statistic ($F = 6.71$, $P < 0.001$). Univariate variance tests suggested that this dissimilarity occurs only in PC I ($F = 19.29$, $P < 0.001$; PC II: $F = 1.75$, $P > 0.05$). Multiple comparison analyses showed that western Ecuadorian populations significantly differ from *R. horribilis* ($P < 0.01$), and from eastern Ecuadorian populations ($P < 0.01$) for PC I.

Morphometric analysis

Multivariate analysis of morphometric characters (using both linear and geometric morphometric approaches) showed differences among western Ecuadorian population (*R. sp. nov.*), *R. horribilis* (Central American population), and eastern Ecuador populations (*R. marina*). As variations in size (measured by SVL) within populations were typically significant across sexes ($P < 0.05$ for both western and eastern Ecuadorian populations), while not significant for the Central American population ($P > 0.05$), we used size-corrected morphometric variables of adult individuals for subsequent analyses. Despite differences in size, males and females did not

differ significantly in size-corrected PC I within populations (see below; all $P < 0.05$; Supporting Information, Fig. S2). Therefore, we pooled data from males and females in our subsequent analysis.

Results from the PCA on linear variables showed most of the variables having high loadings (mainly Femur Length, Head Width, Tibia Length, Third Finger Length and Foot Length) on the first component (31.12% of the variation explained). The second component (15.23% of the variation explained) was mainly based on Interorbital Distance, while the third component (10.54% of the variation explained) was mainly based on Tympanum Diameter (Table 4). Although there is a wide overlap in 2D morpho-space between western Ecuadorian populations and eastern Ecuadorian, and Central American populations (Fig. 7), results from MANOVA show differences among populations for the first three PC's as determined by Pillai's trace test statistic ($F = 11.45$, $P < 0.001$). Univariate variance tests suggest that this dissimilarity occurs in only the first two PCs individually (PC I: $F = 33.63$, $P < 0.001$; PC II: $F = 3.48$, $P < 0.05$; PC III: $F = 2.44$, $P > 0.05$). Multiple comparison analyses showed that toads from the western Ecuadorian populations differed from toads from *R. horribilis* only for PC I ($P < 0.001$), and from toads from eastern Ecuadorian populations for PC II ($P < 0.05$). Overall, individuals from western Ecuador were significantly smaller ($P < 0.001$), but with proportionally larger femur, wider head, larger tibia, and longer third finger (*R. sp. nov.*; \bar{x} SVL= 94.08; \bar{x} FEL/SVL= 41.93%; \bar{x} HW/SVL= 39.94%; \bar{x} TL/SVL= 41.51%; \bar{x} TF/FL= 33.23%, respectively; Fig. 8) than individuals of *R. horribilis* (\bar{x} SVL= 117.34; \bar{x} FEL/SVL = 38.28%; \bar{x} HW/SVL = 37.66%; \bar{x} TL/SVL = 38.26; \bar{x} TF/FL = 28.06%, respectively; Fig. 8). Western Ecuadorian populations tended to have proportionally shorter interorbital distance (\bar{x} IOD/HW= 37.17%) than individuals from eastern Ecuador (*R. marina*; \bar{x} IOD/HW = 38.74%; see Supporting

information, Table S3). Similar results were obtained when we repeated the MANOVA and *post hoc* comparisons on PC I, PC II and PC III only with males (i.e. western Ecuadorian populations differed from eastern Ecuadorian populations and marginally differed from Central American populations in PC I, and from eastern Ecuadorian populations for PC III [Supporting information, Table S4]); and only with females (i.e. western Ecuadorian populations differed from Central American populations in PC I, and marginally differed from eastern Ecuadorian populations for PC II [(Supporting information, Table S4)].

Canonical variate analysis on size-corrected linear variables showed significant morphological differentiation among Central American, eastern, and western Ecuadorian populations (*Wilk's* $\lambda = 0.28$, $\chi^2 = 123.76$, $P < 0.001$). The first canonical factor had an eigenvalue of 1.80, accounted for 86.90% of the total variability, and mainly separated toads from western Ecuadorian populations from Central America and eastern Ecuadorian populations, despite some overlap (Fig. 9). Third Finger Length, Head Width, Thumb Length and Head Length were the strongest discriminators along this factor (Supporting information, Table S5). Overall, individuals from Central America (*R. horribilis*) have proportionally shorter third fingers and narrower heads than individuals from western Ecuador and individuals from Amazonia and eastern Andes of Ecuador (see Supporting information, Table S3). The second canonical factor (13.10% of the total variability) had an eigenvalue of 0.27, and mainly separated toads of western Ecuadorian populations (*R. sp. nov.*) from Amazonian Ecuadorian (*R. marina*) and Central American populations (*R. horribilis*; Fig. 9). Tibia Length stood out as the most important variable for the discrimination of populations along this factor (Supporting information, Table S5; see Supporting information, Table S3).

The PCA applied to shape variables also showed partial overlap among clades in the space of the first two components (Supporting information, Fig. S3). These two Relative Warps explained 74.60% of the total variation (RW 1 = 66.95%; RW 2 = 7.65%; Supporting information, Table S6). Results from MANOVA indicated differences among populations for the first two RW axes as determined by Pillai's trace test statistic ($F = 5.61, P < 0.001$). Univariate variance tests suggested that this dissimilarity occurs only in RW 2 ($F = 9.10, P < 0.001$; RW 1: $F = 2.57, P > 0.05$). Multiple comparison analyses indicated that western Ecuadorian populations differed only from *R. horribilis* for RW 2 ($P < 0.001$).

Canonical variate analysis (CVA) on shape variables (i.e. partial warp scores) showed separation among the three clades along the first (53.85% of the total variability) and second (46.15%) canonical factors (Table 5). Both canonical components were statistically significant ($P < 0.01$), with eigenvalues of 2.42 and 2.07, respectively, suggesting that some aspect of skull shape strongly separates the three studied populations (Fig. 10). Thin-plate splines deformation grids along CV I showed skull shape differences between western Ecuadorian and eastern Ecuadorian populations, especially around the premaxilla and the nasal bone (landmarks 1,2,3 and 4,7; Fig. 10). The western Ecuadorian specimens tended to display a relatively narrower premaxilla, but more elongated nasal bones than eastern populations. Deformations grids along CV II showed differences between western Ecuador (*R. sp. nov.*) and *R. horribilis* (Fig. 10), mainly around the quadratojugal and squamosal bones (landmarks 10, 12, 13), and the distal region of the frontoparietals (landmark 5). A depression of the quadratojugal-squamosal region, and elongation of the distal part of frontoparietal bones distinguished western Ecuador (*R. sp. nov.*) from *R. horribilis*.

Climatic analysis

The PCA on climatic variables (Fig. 11) resulted in four PCs with eigenvalues > 1.0 . These four PCs accounted for 92.86% of the total variation (Table 6). The MANOVA showed differences among populations as determined by Pillai's trace test statistic ($F = 60.23$, $P < 0.001$), however, univariate variance tests suggested that this dissimilarity did not occur in PC I (PC I: $F = 2.65$, $P > 0.05$; PC II: $F = 66.08$, $P < 0.001$; PC III: $F = 85.77$, $P < 0.001$; PC IV: $F = 9.19$, $P < 0.001$). Along PC II (33.04% of the variation explained, mainly by precipitation variables; Table 6), western Ecuadorian populations differed from Central America and eastern Ecuadorian populations (both $P < 0.001$; Fig. 11). Along PC III (16.49% of the variation explained, mainly by temperature seasonality variables; Table 6), western Ecuadorian populations separated only from Central America (Fig. 11). Overall, western Ecuadorian populations tend to occur in drier and less seasonal areas than other populations (Fig. 11). Along PC IV (8.71% of the total variance, mainly mean diurnal range; Table 6), western Ecuadorian populations differed from both Central American and eastern Ecuadorian populations (both $P < 0.001$).

Our analyses of mtDNA, linear morphometrics, geometric morphometrics of cranial shape, calls, and climatic envelopes reveal consistent differences between populations from western Ecuador, corresponding to Clade B in our phylogeny, and populations of *R. horribilis* from Central America. Because the type locality of *R. horribilis* is in Central America, we assign that binomial to the Central American populations. As far as we know, there are no prior binomials available for the populations from western Ecuador. Therefore, we conclude that those populations represent a new species, which we describe below.

Remarks on the availability of names applicable to the new species

Within the potential distribution range of the new species there are two available names that could be available for the new species:

a) *Bufo pithecodactylus* (Werner, 1899). According to the original publication, the type locality “La Unión” is on the western slopes of Eastern Cordillera, near Bogotá.

Nearby records in iNaturalist (e.g., observations Nos. 57911460 and 11998145) are identified as *Rhinella horribilis*. We were not able to obtain genetic sequences from these areas to validate these identifications. However, we did obtain five genetic sequences from specimens collected in “Santander, Reserva Cabildo Verde”

(Guarnizo *et al.*, 2015), also on the West side of the Colombian Eastern Cordillera, approximately 250 km airline distance from Bogotá. Our phylogenetic analysis (see Supporting Information, Fig. S4) place these five specimens within the *R. horribilis sensu stricto* clade. The geographic proximity and lack of conspicuous geographic barriers between the type locality of *Bufo pithecodactylus* and the genetic samples from Santander strongly suggest that they are conspecific. In contrast, the type locality of *Bufo pithecodactylus* is separated from the distribution range of *R. horribilis* by the central and occidental Andean cordilleras and a longer geographic distance (~650 km). Therefore, we conclude that “*B. pithecodactylus*” is not conspecific with the new species but a junior synonym of *R. horribilis*.

b) *Bufo marinus* var. *fluminensis* (Jiménez de la Espada, 1875) was described based on at least 10 syntypes (González-Fernández, 2006; Frost, 2023) collected by Jiménez de la Espada within a large geographic range, practically throughout the entire South American continent: "la cuenca del Guayas o rio de Guayaquil", Ecuador; "provincia

de Rio-Janeiro", Brazil; "Fazenda imperial de Santa Cruz, á 14 leguas de la capital", Brazil; "Bahia", Brazil; "Rio-Janeiro y la Tijuca", Brazil: "Tabatinga, orillas del Amazonas y frontera del Perú y Brasil"; "Fazenda Santa Cruz", Brazil; "Chonana", Ecuador; and "Babahoyo", Ecuador according to De la Riva (2000); Therefore, the type material should include at least three species of the *Rhinella marina* species group (De la Riva, 2000), including the new species. To avoid the ambiguity in the applicability of this name, we now designate as lectotype for *Bufo marinus* var. *fluminensis* a specimen with an unambiguous description of its collection locality, within the geographic range of *R. marina sensu stricto*: MNCN 3076 (Tabatinga, orillas del Amazonas y frontera del Perú y Brasil). The lectotype was collected by M. Jiménez de la Espada in September 1865 (González-Fernández, 2006; González-Fernández et al. 2009, Frost, 2023). This would leave the western Ecuadorian population with no available name as suggested by Frost (2023).

***RHINELLA BELLA* SP. NOV.**

(FIGS 12, 13, 14, 15; TABLE S8)

Holotype (Fig. 12): QCAZ 23305, adult male, SVL = 87.11 mm, collected in Ecuador, Guayas Province, between Palmas and Balsas (ca. 2.003° S, 80.562° W) at 72 m.a.s.l., on 18 March 2003 by Santiago Ron.

Paratypes: Juveniles (Fig. 14): QCAZ 13893, collected in Cañar Canton, Manta Real Community (ca. 2.554° S, 79.364° W) at 1100 m.a.s.l., on 21 December 1998 by Ricardo Oliva. QCAZ 28528, collected in Santo Domingo Canton, near to secondary road, near Tinalandia,

jumping between puddles, (ca. 0.303° S, 79.041° W) at 694 m.a.s.l., on 05 January 2005 by Giovanna Romero. QCAZ 35433, collected in Pichincha Province, Pedro Vicente Maldonado, 6 Km to the Northwest at airport, (ca. 0.104° S, 79.103° W) at 544 m.a.s.l., on 17 April 2003 by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 40424, collected in Esmeraldas Province, Rosa Zarate Parish, Laguna del Cube, (ca. 0.415° S, 79.650° W) at 207 m.a.s.l., on 22 August 2007 by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 45989 and 46001, collected in Imbabura Province, Cotacachi-Cayapas Reserve buffer zone, near the Aguas Verdes River, (ca. 0.331° S, 78.931° W) at 670 m.a.s.l., on 01 November 2009 by Diego Almeida. QCAZ 49447, collected in Manabí Province, Jama Canton, Reserva Lalo Loor Locality, (ca. 0.079° S, 80.148° W) at 150 m.a.s.l., on 02 September 2010 by Diego Salazar. QCAZ 50701 and 50702, collected in Manabí Province, 5 km north of Rocafuerte, San Andrés de Rocafuerte Locality, (ca. 0.868° S, 80.464° W) at 334 m.a.s.l., on 26 by Santiago Ron. **Adult males** (Fig. 13): QCAZ 12039, collected in Santo Domingo Province, 5 km north of Rocafuerte, Hotel Saracay Locality, (ca. 0.676° S, 76.399° W) at 334 m.a.s.l., on 05 April 1998 by Luis Eduardo López. QCAZ 17965, collected in Pichincha Province, Guayllabamba, under the bridge over the Guayllabamba river, (ca. 0.069° S, 78.372° W) at 1972 m.a.s.l., on 23 November 2001 by Verónica Sandoya. QCAZ 23324, collected in Santa Elena Province, Via Palmas-Balsas Locality, (ca. 2.031° S, 80.460° W) at 78 m.a.s.l., on 23 November 2001 by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 23486, collected in Guayas Province, Sendero de Cerro Más Vale Locality, in stone, in Cerro Blanco stream approximately 200 m, (ca. 2.399° S, 79.634° W) on 22 March 2003 by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 24579, collected in Manabí Province, Puerto Rico, Alándaluz Locality, in lagoon facing the north side beach, (ca. 1.640° S, 80.830° W) 18 February 2002 by David Cannatella. QCAZ 39353, collected in Pichincha Province, Tababela, New Quito International Airport, N-2 reservoir, at the edge of a water reservoir, (ca. 0.181° S, 78.334° W), on 09

September 2008 by Fernando Ayala. QCAZ 41327, collected in Guayas Province, Bosque Protector Cerro Blanco Locality, (ca. 2.182° S, 80.018 W), at 237 m.a.s.l., on 17 March 2008 by Gustavo Pazmiño. QCAZ 47444 and 47445, collected in Loja Province, San Bernabé Locality, (ca. 4.113° S, 79.304 W), at 1665 m.a.s.l., on 03 March 2010 by Elicio Tapia. **Adult females** (Fig. 13): QCAZ 50698, collected in Manabi Province, Puerto Cayo Locality, (ca. 1.344° S, 80.732 W), at 29 m.a.s.l., on 25 February 2011 by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 50703, collected in San Andrés de Rocafuerte, 5 km north of Rocafuerte, (ca. -0.86822, -80.46363) at 334 m.a.s.l by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 47192, collected on the shore of the Vance River in Esmeraldas Province, (ca. 0.3269719, -79.47686) by Melina Samaniego. QCAZ 33775, 33778-79, 33782-83, collected in Alluriquín, Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas Province, (ca. -0.320309, -78.99347) by Elicio Tapia. QCAZ 26345, collected 2.7 km north of Oña in Azuay Province, (ca. -3.454261, -79.16227) at 2386 m.a.s.l by Ítalo Tapia. QCAZ 26320, collected in Oña, Azuay Province, (ca. -3.46123, -79.16253) by Luis Coloma. QCAZ 17966-69, collected under the bridge over the Guayllabamba river in Guayllabamba, Pichincha Province, (ca. -0.068925, -78.37195) at 1972 m.a.s.l by Verónica Sandoya. QCAZ 1992-93, collected in Santo Domingo de los Colorados, Pichincha Province, on the road to Quevedo, (ca. -0.256950, -79.16612) by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 1994-97, 1999, collected in Tonsupa, Esmeraldas Province, (ca. 0.8852820, -79.80499) by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 2001, collected in Guayaquil suburbio, Guayas Province, (ca. -2.257000, -79.87800) by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 2258-59, 2263-64, collected in Tonsupa, Esmeraldas Province, (ca. 0.8852820, -79.80499) by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 2265, collected in Santo Domingo de los Colorados, Pichincha Province, (ca. -0.256950, -79.16612) by Santiago Ron. QCAZ 2267, collected in the suburbs of Guayaquil, Guayas Province, (ca. -4.2396, -79.2196) by

Santiago Ron. QCAZ 10497, collected in Chalcápac, Valle de Yunguilla, Vía Girón Pasaje, Azuay Province, (ca. -3.233333, -79.2) at 1550 m.a.s.l by Santiago Ron.

Suggested common names:

Cane toad (EN) or Beautiful Cane toad (English); Sapo Bello de la Caña (Spanish).

Assignment of new species:

We assign the new species to the genus *Rhinella* based on the phylogeny. We assign the new species to the *Rhinella* marina species group (sensu Pereyra et al. 2021) based on the phylogeny and the synapomorphy “sacral diapophyses with the anterior edge angled posteriorly to the midline axis of the vertebral column”. The other synapomorphy of this group listed by Pereyra *et al.* (2021; i.e. “jagged or scalloped articulation between the medial ramus of pterygoid and parasphenoid alae”) could not be examined. *R. bella* sp. nov. also shares the following characters with other members of the *R. marina* group, which, when used in combination, let to differentiate the species from other *Rhinella* groups (8 out of 12 characters listed by Pereyra *et al.* (2021) were examined): Preorbital crest well developed, supraorbital crest well developed, pretympanic crest well developed, nasal and frontoparietal articulate along the entire margin, inguinal fat bodies, parotid gland approximately ellipsoid, longer than wide or triangular and bulky, tarsal fold, and extensor digitorum longus with an insertion on the metatarsophalangeal joint of digiti IV (Supporting Information, Table S7).

Definition:

(Figs. 12, 13, 15): *Rhinella bella* sp. nov. is characterized by: (1) average SVL in adult females 102.16 mm ($SD = 13.75$, $n = 29$), adult males 86.51 mm ($SD = 13.95$, $n = 31$; see Supporting information, Table S8); (2) short snout, subacuminated in dorsal view, truncated to rounded in profile; (3) bony knob at angle of jaws absent; (4) low and thick cephalic crests with

borders with keratinized spicules, continuous with supraorbital, supratympanic, canthal, rostral and preorbital crests; reduced infraorbital crests, and preorbital crests absent; (5) heel not reaching posterior margin of eye when hindlimbs depressed; (6) vertebral apophyses absent; (7) dorsal skin with medium and round tubercles usually with a keratinized spicule at the tip, with or without large scattered warts, most are pointed; (8) a thin middorsal line from snout to groin is present; (9) absence of dorsolateral fringe; (10) tympanic membrane and tympanic annulus distinct; (11) parotoid glands relatively big, elongate posteriorly, relatively prominent in dorsal view, with visible small pores, and with a keratinized spicule at the posterior tip, width of parotoid glands varies from 9.17 to 14.27% of SVL; height of parotoid glands can vary from 15.91 to 22.44% of SVL; (12) upper eyelid with keratinized warts; (13) palms without rudimentary basal webbing between fingers, lateral fringes absent; small rounded knobs at tips of digits; finger lengths $3 > 4 > 2 > 1$; (14) inner and outer metatarsal tubercles conical, protruding distally, outer usually similar size of inner tubercles; subarticular tubercles present; supernumerary tubercles with keratinized spicule at the tip, distributed linearly on toes on plantar surface; (15) forelimbs and forearms robust with low and rounded warts keratinized; supernumerary tubercles rounded with different size, distributed irregularly on palm; palmar tubercle larger than thenar tubercle, both are oval; (16) foot with basal webbing between toes, lateral fringes present; small rounded knobs at tips of digits; toe lengths $4 > 5 > 3 > 2 > 1$; (16) nuptial pads present.

Diagnosis:

Rhinella bella sp. nov. is morphologically similar to *R. horribilis* and *R. marina*.

However, *R. bella* sp. nov. differs from populations of *R. horribilis* by having a smaller body size, along with proportionally larger femur, wider head, and larger tibia (Fig. 8; Supporting

information, Table S3; S8). Differences among species were also evident in the skull shape (see results of morphometric analyses). Acevedo *et al.* (2016) reported cranial morphology differences between populations of east (*R. marina*) and west (*R. horribilis*) side of the Venezuelan Andes, mainly around the pre-maxillar, nasal bones, and occipital region. We also found skull differences between populations on the eastern (*R. marina*) versus western (***R. bella* sp. nov.**) sides of the Ecuadorian Andes, mainly concerning the pre-maxillar and nasal bones. However, the non-monophyletic status of the eastern and Amazon Basin populations (Vallinoto *et al.*, 2010; this paper) precluded us from making further comparisons with the findings of Acevedo *et al.* (2016). The new species is distinguishable from *R. horribilis* by a depressed area on the quadratojugal-squamosal contact region, and the elongation of frontoparietal bones at their most distant region (Fig. 10; Table 5).

***Rhinella bella* sp. nov.** differs in environmental envelope from *R. horribilis* and *R. marina* (Fig. 11; Table 6; for details see Climatic analysis section from Methods and Results) and is separated by high genetic distances from both species as well (Fig. 3; Table 1; see Molecular phylogenetic analysis from Methods and Results).

Advertisement calls of ***R. bella* sp. nov.** are significantly shorter, with fewer notes and shorter rise time than those of *R. horribilis* and *R. marina* (Fig. 4; Table 2). The number of notes per call of ***R. bella* sp. nov.** (midrange = 23; range 6 – 40) is also lower than those reported in other species of the *R. marina* group (e.g. *R. arenarum* [midrange = 84, range 61 – 107; Straneck *et al.*, 1993]; *R. marina* [midrange = 176.5, range 18 – 335; present work]; *R. poeppigii* [midrange = 27.5, range 10 – 45; De la Riva *et al.*, 1996]; and *R. diptycha* [midrange = 36.5, range 33 – 40; Köhler *et al.*, 1997]). Furthermore, ***R. bella* sp. nov.** produce calls with higher dominant frequency than *R. horribilis* and *R. marina* (Fig. 6; Table 2, 3).

Description of holotype:

Adult male; robust body; head wider (HW = 36.15 mm) than long (HL = 30.49 mm). Head shape in dorsal view subtriangular with short, squared snout and straight lateral view, tip of the snout not surpassing anterior margin of maxilla in dorsal and ventral views. Numerous rounded tubercles with several keratinized spicules in dorsum. Scattered granulation on top of the head. Presence of low cephalic crests with keratinized borders, continuous with supraorbital, supratympanic, canthal rostral and preorbital crests; reduced infraorbital crests, and preorbital crests absent. Tympanic membrane and tympanic annulus distinct; bony knob at angle of jaws absent; corner of mouth angular; vertebral apophyses absent; parotoid glands relatively big, elongate posteriorly, relatively prominent in dorsal view, with small pores visible, and tubercles keratinized; upper eyelid with keratinized warts. Forelimbs and forearms robust with low and rounded keratinized warts. A longitudinal mid-dorsal cream thin raphe is present from the snout to near the cloacal region. Hand without basal webbing between fingers, lateral fringes absent; small, rounded knobs at tips of digits; finger lengths $3 > 4 > 2 > 1$; subarticular tubercles low and rounded; supernumerary tubercles rounded, distributed irregularly on palm; palmar tubercle larger than thenar tubercle, both are oval; nuptial pads on the dorsolateral surface of fingers I and II. Foot longer than tibia (TL/FL = 0.948); foot with basal webbing between toes, lateral fringes present; small, rounded knobs at tips of digits; toe lengths $4 > 5 > 3 > 2 > 1$; inner and outer metatarsal tubercles conical, protruding distally, outer similar size of inner tubercles (~ 4.18 mm); subarticular tubercles present; supernumerary keratinized tubercles rounded distributed linearly on toes on plantar surface.

Color of holotype in preservative:

(Fig. 12): Dorsum light gray, rounded tubercles on dorsum between light cream and dark brown with dark brown spicules, also in dorsal surfaces of tights, shanks, and forelimbs which are lighter than dorsum; few dark gray marks arranged irregularly on dorsum. Nuptial pads dark brown. Ventral surfaces gray becoming yellowish-cream with irregular dark brown marks medially; cream color with black edges slightly posterior to gular region. Fingertips and subarticular tubercles yellowish-cream. Dark brown knobs at tips of digits; Tympanum dark gray (Fig. 12).

Etymology: “*Bella*”, in Latin meaning “beautiful”, in contradiction to “*horribilis*”, the name of its sister species. We think that “*horribilis*” is an undeserved name that stems from anachronistic views of nature common in the XIX century. Judgements of the beauty of organisms are highly subjective, something that we highlight with the name of the new species. Additionally, the precise geographic transition between *R. bella* sp. nov. and *R. horribilis* is still unknown, just as is the border between beauty and ugliness.

Variation of coloration in preserved specimens:

(Figs. 12, 13): Background dorsal coloration varies from light gray (e.g. QCAZ 23305, 50698, 50701) to dark brown (e.g. QCAZ 41327,24579, 39353), with irregular black and yellowish marks (e.g. QCAZ 40806, 50702, 50698). A thin middorsal line from snout to groin is present, except QCAZ 47445. Ventral surfaces have a yellowish-cream to dark brown background; and several with irregular grey marks arranged in diverse patterns (e.g. QCAZ 12039, 17965 28528), absence in QCAZ 41327, 47445, 47444.

Variation of coloration in live individuals:

(Fig. 15): Color variation of in life individuals is shown in Fig. 15.

Vocalization: Based on 17 males recorded at six localities from western Ecuador, the advertisement call of *R. bella* sp. nov. is a short trill with a mean duration of 1.51 s (range 0.94 – 2.56 s), a mean call rise time of 0.94 s (range 0.65 – 1.79) and a mean dominant frequency of 803.05 Hz (range 668.00 – 961.83 Hz). The call consists of 10 – 34 notes, with 2 – 5 pulses per note. The mean pulse rate is 91.31 pulses per second (range 66.95 – 113.08 pulses per second), and the mean call repetition rate is 8.57 calls per minute (range 5 – 14 calls per minute; Table 3).

Distribution, ecology and conservation status:

This species is restricted to the western side of the Andes, from the sea level up to 2900 m.a.s.l. Among Ecuadorian amphibians, it has one of the widest elevation ranges and occurs in six out of ten natural regions: Chocó Tropical Rainforest, Coastal Deciduous Forest, Coastal Dry Scrubland, Inter-Andean Scrubland, Western Montane Forest, and Western Piedmont Forest (regions as defined by *Ron et al.*, 2022). It is most frequently found in artificial open areas including agricultural fields, grasslands, urban, and suburban habitats. It occurs infrequently in undisturbed forests. Reproduction takes place in ponds, rivers, and swamps. Reproductive activity (calling males or amplexant pairs) have been observed mainly in April, June, and July. As in other species of the *R. marina* species group, eggs are deposited in strings in water. Tadpoles are aquatic and have a high resistance to heat, up to 42.5 °C (*Pintanel et al.*, 2022). The complete distribution of *R. bella* sp. nov. remains unknown, mainly due to lack of distributional information in the Colombian Chocó Bioregion. Ecuadorian localities in northern Ecuador are close to the border with Colombia. Nearby Colombian records of “*R. horribilis*” in iNaturalist (e.g., observations numbers 36168677 in Llorente, San Andrés de Tumaco and 102430734 in Tumaco) morphologically resemble *R. bella* sp. nov. and we consider them unconfirmed records of *R. bella* sp. nov. in Colombia. Moreover, the limited seasonal temperature variation of the

Colombian Chocó Bioregion matches the climatic envelope of the *R. bella* sp. nov., further suggesting its occurrence in southern of Colombia (see results of climatic envelopes and Fig. 11; Table 6). This species also occurs in northwestern of Peru, south to 6° S of latitude (reported as “*R. horribilis*” by Armijos-Ojeda et al. 2021).

The new species occurs in the following protected areas: Reserva Ecológica Manglares Churute, Reserva Ecológica Los Ilinizas, Parque Nacional Machalilla, Reserva Ecológica Mache Chindul, Reserva Tesoro Escondido, Bosque Protector Mindo-Nambillo, Centro Científico Río Palenque, Bosque Petrificado de Puyango, Bosque Integral Otonga, Estación Biológica Bilsa (Páez-Rosales & Ron 2022 as “*R. horribilis*”). The new species can be abundant in artificial open areas. Its tolerance of habitat disturbance, large distribution range along a wide elevation gradient, diverse Natural Regions (six different regions in Ecuador, one of the highest among Ecuadorian anurans) allow us to recommend its assignment to the Least Concern category in the Red List (based on the IUCN guidelines).

DISCUSSION

Our analyses reveal that populations from western Ecuador represent an independent lineage from all other known species of the *Rhinella marina* group. We base this conclusion on the congruence observed between genetic, bioacoustic, morphological and climate envelope information. Western Ecuadorian populations are highly different genetically from other species of the group. Its mtDNA divergence is much higher that observed between uncontroversial species pairs of the same group like *R. arenarum* and *R. icterica* or *R. diptycha* and *R. poeppigii*. Differences in advertisement calls are additional, clear indications that those populations represent a candidate species within the *R. marina* group. We provide conclusive evidence, based

on an integrative approach combining different sources of information, that there are two, independent lineages of *R. marina* group toads west of the Andes in northern South America and Central America. One, *R. horribilis*, ranges north through Central America as far as southern Texas whereas the other, ***R. bella* sp. nov.**, occurs in Ecuador and probably as far north as southwestern Colombia and as far south as extreme northern Peru.

Past studies have shown two genetically distinct species within *R. marina* from east and west side of the Venezuelan Andes (Slade & Moritz, 1998), including the recent work of Acevedo *et al.* (2016), who suggested that the *R. horribilis* name should be revalidated for the western Andes and Central American populations. Additionally, Mulcahy *et al.* (2006), Pramuk (2006) and Vallinoto *et al.* (2010) had previously found important levels of genetic divergence between Central American and Ecuadorian samples, however, the incomplete sampling (only very few were included from western Ecuador) and the lack of bioacoustics, morphological (but see Pramuk, 2006) and ecological information, limited their conclusions. We provide novel evidence showing an independent evolutionary lineage consistent with a separate species, within the *R. marina* species group, confirming that the western Ecuadorian populations (***R. bella* sp. nov.**) are a new, species distinct from the populations of Central America (*R. horribilis*), and from the populations from the Amazon basin (*R. marina*).

In contrast to the cryptic morphological diversity notable throughout the genus *Rhinella* (Graybeal, 1997; Pramuk, 2006; Acevedo *et al.*, 2016), including the *R. marina* species group, our morphometric analyses (including the geometric morphometric-based) suggest that ***R. bella* sp. nov.** (western Ecuadorian populations) is overtly distinguishable from *R. horribilis* (Central American populations) and from *R. marina* (Amazon basin populations) as currently understood. Isolated from all other *R. marina* group toads except for *R. horribilis* by the Andes, ***R. bella* sp.**

nov. appears to be among the most geographically isolated and morphologically distinctive of this group of species.

We report significant acoustic differences between *R. horribilis*, *R. marina* and ***R. bella* sp. nov.** (see Fig. 4, 5, 6) despite the generally conservative structure of advertisement calls among species of the *R. marina* group (Maciel *et al.*, 2007). The distinctly lower number of notes per call in ***R. bella* sp. nov.** relative to other species within the *R. marina* group is significant. Similarly, the higher dominant frequency of ***R. bella* sp. nov.** calls in comparison with calls of *R. horribilis* and *R. marina* is remarkable as this call trait is among the few not strongly dependent on operational temperature (Fig. 6), and has been proven to be useful to assess species limits (Köhler *et al.*, 2017). This acoustic distinctiveness of ***R. bella* sp. nov.** among *R. marina* group species, and especially from *R. horribilis*, suggests that calls may have diverged at faster rates compared to morphology in this group, as it has also been shown in other anuran species groups (e.g. Padial *et al.*, 2008; Angulo & Icochea, 2010; Funk *et al.*, 2012). These patterns could be due to sexual selection promoting rapid divergence in both male traits and female preferences, or strong selection on species recognition (Panhuis *et al.*, 2001). This may be particularly relevant to the calls of ***R. bella* sp. nov.** vs. *R. horribilis* in that vocal character displacement where these two species meet (probably in southern Colombia) could promote mating isolation.

Alternatively, mate-recognition traits as calls, may diverge faster than morphology due to a strong stabilizing selection on morphological traits (Funk *et al.*, 2012), which may be imposed by several ecological factors (Bickford *et al.*, 2007). Previous studies have not fully evaluated call differences within the *R. marina* species group, although acoustic information seems to be particularly useful for the delimitation of cryptic species (Funk *et al.*, 2012).

The comparison of climatic envelopes among studied populations provided important complementary evidence for species separation (see Fig. 11). Toad populations occurring in western Ecuador (*R. bella* sp. nov.) have a climatic envelope with lesser temperature seasonality than populations of *R. horribilis* occurring further north in South America and Central America. Temperature seasonality can be a major climatic factor limiting dispersal of amphibians (Wiens *et al.*, 2006), and Neotropical anurans demonstrate climatic specializations along temperature seasonality axes (Graham *et al.*, 2004). We would not expect notable and substantial morphological divergence between *R. bella* sp. nov. and *R. horribilis* if speciation occurred mainly via geographic isolation related to climatic components unless climate imposed selection on morphology. However, the relative importance of climatic factors in population divergence and speciation of these lineages deserves further investigation.

We also found that *R. marina* from the Amazon Basin remains non-monophyletic, as was previously found by Vallinoto *et al.* (2010) and Rivera *et al.* (2022). Samples of *R. marina* are nested within only one well supported clade (clade E in Figure 2) as the sample MJH 3678 of “*R. marina*” from clade D is probably misidentified and most likely corresponds to *R. poeppigii*. Clade E is composed of “*R. poeppigii*” from Bolivia, *R. diptycha*, *R. marina* from the eastern side of Ecuadorian Andes, and *R. marina* from the Amazonian Basin. The sample MNCN/ADN6044 of *R. poeppigii*, however, is likely misidentified and corresponds to either *R. marina* or *R. diptycha*. Furthermore, corroborating Vallinoto *et al.* (2010) and Ron *et al.* (2015), our results placed *R. crucifer* as sister to the *R. marina* group according to mtDNA sequence information. Although *R. crucifer* is not formally considered to be in the *R. marina* species group (Pramuk, 2006), morphological similarities and a close cytogenetic and phylogenetic relationship

between it and members of the *R. marina* group have been noted previously (Blair, 1972; Cei, 1972; Duellman & Schulte, 1992; Baldissera *et al.*, 1999; Pauly *et al.*, 2004; Pramuk, 2006).

The discrepancy between phylogenetic relationships and the taxonomic classification of species within the *R. marina* species group could be influenced by several factors. First, the lack of an integrative taxonomy (i.e. species delimitation based on multiple sources of evidence; Padial *et al.*, 2010) that provides a more effective solution to refine the systematics of the *R. marina* species group. Second, DNA sequences of some lineages (e.g. some populations previously known as *R. horribilis*) available for only a small number of samples and/or with limited representation of the geographic distribution (Maciel *et al.*, 2010; Vallinoto *et al.*, 2010). Third, the evident lack of prominent diagnostic morphological characters for some lineages in this group can result in the misidentification of specimens. For instance, Venegas & Ron (2014) reported on 10 specimens of *R. poeppigii* deposited at Museo de Zoología, Pontificia Universidad Católica del Ecuador (QCAZ) that had previously been misidentified as *R. marina*. Finally, genetic introgression resulting from interspecific hybridization, which is known to occur among numerous closely related species of Bufonid toads in sympatry (e.g. Masta *et al.*, 2002; Smith & Green, 2004), may confound phylogenetic reconstruction by obscuring topology and divergence estimates. This could be the case for some populations of *R. marina* and *R. diptycha* in the Amazon Basin (Sequeira *et al.*, 2011) and will likely continue to present challenges for delineating species boundaries within the entire *R. marina* group east of the Andes (Rivera *et al.* 2022). West of the Andes, however, the genetic differentiation between ***R. bella* sp. nov.** and *R. horribilis* is clearly demonstrable, although the nature and extent of any putative contact zone between the two species, possibly in southwest Colombia and/or extreme northwest Ecuador, remain unknown.

Cane Toads are economically important and invasive outside of their native range, having been introduced on many Caribbean and Pacific islands (Easteal, 1981, 1985; Lever, 2001; Shine, 2010, 2018), where they are often now considered pests. The impact of such a large, voracious, prolific and toxic amphibian on the ecology of northern Australia, for example, has been profound (Shine, 2018). Most of the evidence and historical record indicates that the Cane Toads currently in the Pacific originated from native populations in Venezuela, via Puerto Rico, Cuba and Florida (Slade & Moritz, 1998). Considering the extent of cryptic taxonomic diversity of *R. marina* species toads, however, and the probability that new species such as *R. bella* sp. nov. remain to be discovered within the complex, it is possible that the Cane Toads infesting Australia and many Pacific Islands may not actually be *R. marina*. If this is the case, some aspects of our current knowledge on global biological invasions of these species (e.g. Tingley *et al.*, 2014) would deserve reconsideration.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

Raw morphometric data for the new species are presented as Supporting Information, Table S9 [this table will be added if the manuscript is accepted]. All DNA sequences will be uploaded to GenBank (Table S1). Calls from QCAZ museum are available at <https://bioweb.bio/>.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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FIGURES

Figure 1. Distribution of *Rhinella horribilis* from Central America (black circles; according to Acevedo *et al.*, 2016), *R. bella* sp. nov. (white circles; according to our results; previously *R. horribilis* according to Acevedo *et al.*, 2016), and *R. marina sensu lato* (black triangles). Only locations of sequenced specimens are shown (in this study and from GenBank; see main text and Supporting information, Table S1).

Figure 2. Phylogenetic relationships among species of the *Rhinella marina* group based on the Bayesian analysis of the 12S–16S fragment. Numbers above the branches are Bayesian posterior probability values and maximum likelihood bootstrap values. Posterior probabilities higher than 0.9, and maximum parsimony bootstrap values higher than 90% are marked with an asterisk (*). Clade A corresponds to *R. horribilis*, Clade B to *R. bella* sp. nov., Clades D most probably to *R. poeppigii* (see Discussion section) and clade E to *R. marina*.

Figure 3. Multidimensional scaling plot of the pairwise genetic distances calculated between species of *Rhinella marina* group (see Table 1). Clade B corresponds to the new species *R. bella* sp. nov.. Clade D most probably correspond to *R. poeppigii* (see Discussion section).

Figure 4. Plot of the first two axes (PC's) from principal components analysis (PCA) based on seven acoustic variables of the advertisement calls of 35 toads from western Ecuador (*Rhinella bella* sp. nov.), eastern Ecuador (*R. marina*) and Central America (*R. horribilis*). Additionally, one individual from eastern Peru was included in the analysis.

Figure 5. Calls of: **A-B** *Rhinella bella* **sp. nov.** from Yunguilla, Provincia Azuay, western Ecuador. **C-D** *R. horribilis* from 1.6 km WNW of Villa Neily, Puntaneras, Costa Rica, Central America. **E-F** *R. marina* from Vía Maxus km 58, Provincia Orellana, eastern Ecuador. Oscilograms (A, C and E) and spectrograms (B, D and F).

Figure 6. Violin plot showing the variation (median, range, kernel density, 25th-75th percentiles) of dominant frequency (Hz) of calls in toad populations from Central America ($n = 5$), eastern Ecuador ($n = 12$) and western Ecuador ($n = 17$). Individuals from western Ecuador correspond to *R. bella* **sp. nov.**, individuals from eastern Ecuador correspond to *R. marina*, and individuals from Central America correspond to *R. horribilis*.

Figure 7. Principal components (PC's) from a PCA based on 12 continuously varying lineal and size-corrected morphometric characters from 106 toads (*Rhinella marina* species group; see methods in the main text). Individuals are classified by geographic region, with 70% ellipse per group. For eigenvectors and eigenvalues see Table 4. Individuals from western Ecuador correspond to *R. bella* **sp. nov.**, individuals from eastern Ecuador correspond to *R. marina*, and individuals from Central America correspond to *R. horribilis*.

Figure 8. Violin plots showing the variation (median -unfilled diamond-, range, kernel density, 25th-75th percentiles) of the following measurements (in mm): **A.** Snout-vent length (SVL) of toad populations from Central America ($n = 20$) and western Ecuador ($n = 60$). Individuals from Central America correspond to *Rhinella horribilis* and individuals from western Ecuador correspond to *R. bella* **sp. nov.** **B.** Tympanum diameter as a proportion (in percentage) of head length (TD/HL). **C.** Tibia length as a proportion (in percentage) of snout-vent length (TL/SVL).

D. Head length as a proportion (in percentage) of snout-vent length (HL/SVL). **E.** Head width as a proportion (in percentage) of snout-vent length (HW/SVL).

Figure 9. Plot of the first two canonical axes (I, II) from Canonical Variates Analysis (CVA) based on 13 continuously varying lineal morphological characters from 106 toads of three species from *Rhinella marina* species group (see methods). Individuals from western Ecuador correspond to *R. bella* sp. nov., individuals from eastern Ecuador correspond to *R. marina*, and individuals from Central America correspond to *R. horribilis*.

Figure 10. Morphological differences in skull shape among western Ecuadorian (*Rhinella bella* sp. nov.), eastern Ecuadorian (*R. marina*), and Central American (*R. horribilis*) populations of *R. marina* species group. The plot of the first two canonical axes of Canonical Variates Analysis (CVA) based on shape variables from 84 toads (see methods in the main text), and changes with respect to the average on the deformation grids for the extreme points along each canonical variate axis are shown. Grid differences among populations have been exaggerated five-fold to make them more visible.

Figure 11. Principal components (PC's) from a PCA based on 19 climatic variables from 98 collection localities of specimens used for the phylogenetic analysis. Individuals are classified by geographic region, with 90% ellipse per group. For eigenvectors and eigenvalues see Table 6, Individuals from western Ecuador correspond to *Rhinella bella* sp. nov., individuals from eastern Ecuador correspond to *R. marina*, and individuals from Central America correspond to *R. horribilis*.

Figure 12. Dorsal view (A), lateral view (B) and ventral views of right forelimb (C) and right hind limb (D) of the holotype of *Rhinella bella* sp. nov. (QCAZ 23305; adult male; Guayas Province, between Palmas and Balsas, Ecuador. Not shown at the same scale. Photos by SRR.

Figure 13. Adult preserved specimens of *Rhinella bella* sp. nov. showing variation in dorsal and ventral coloration. From left to right, first row: QCAZ 12039, 17965, 23324 (males); second row: QCAZ 23486, 24579, 39353 (males); third row: QCAZ 41327, 47444, 47445 (males), 50698 (female). See Table S1 for locality data. Specimens not shown at the same scale. Photos by SRR.

Figure 14. Juveniles preserved specimens of *Rhinella bella* sp. nov. showing variation in dorsal and ventral coloration. From left to right, first row: QCAZ 13893, 28528, 35433; second row: QCAZ 40424, 45989, 49447, third row: QCAZ 50701, 50702. See Table S1 for locality data. Specimens not shown at the same scale. Photos by SRR.

Figure 15. Adult in live individuals of *Rhinella bella* sp. nov. showing variation in dorsal and ventral coloration. (A) adult male, QCAZ 51478 (SVL = 84.05mm); (B) adult female, QCAZ 57032 (SVL = 66.85 mm); (C) adult female, QCAZ 51799 (SVL =63.12mm); (D) adult male, QCAZ 68814 (SVL =73.73); (E) adult male, QCAZ 65726 (108.60); (F) adult female, QCAZ 67265 (95.69); (G) adult male, QCAZ 51423 (SVL =83.81); (H) adult male, QCAZ 51308 (SVL =95.33); (I) adult female, QCAZ 51846 (SVL =123.33); (J) adult female, QCAZ 55040 (SVL =102.74). See Table S1 for locality data. Individuals not shown at the same scale. Photos by SRR.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 2. Continuation

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

Figure 10.

Figure 12.

Figure 13.

Figure 14.

Figure 15.

TABLES

Table 1. Genetic uncorrected distances (p) among taxa of *Rhinalla marina* group (based on 16S gene). Values represent the means and the minimum–maximum range of the genetic differentiation among taxa and the main clades shown in the phylogeny of *R. marina* species group. Species names with asterisk belong to Clade C. Clade A corresponds to *R. horribilis*, Clade B to *R. bella* sp. nov., Clade D most probably to *R. poeppigii* (see Discussion section) and E to *R. marina*. *Rhinella crucifer* refers to the outgroup.

	Taxa/Clade	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Clade A	-							
2	Clade B	0.05 0.042–0.061	-						
3	Clade D	0.046 0.042–0.057	0.044 0.037–0.055	-					
4	Clade E	0.049 0.044–0.064	0.043 0.035–0.057	0.02 0.015–0.029	-				
5	<i>R. achavali</i> *	0.052 0.05–0.059	0.048 0.042–0.055	0.029 0.026–0.031	0.029 0.022–0.033	-			
6	<i>R. arenarum</i> *	0.055 0.053–0.061	0.046 0.04–0.053	0.031 0.029–0.033	0.03 0.024–0.035	0.007 0.007–0.007	-		
7	<i>R. crucifer</i>	0.043 0.04–0.051	0.04 0.035–0.044	0.041 0.037–0.046	0.043 0.037–0.048	0.034 0.033–0.035	0.036 0.035–0.037	-	
8	<i>R. icterica</i> *	0.055 0.053–0.061	0.048 0.04–0.057	0.031 0.029–0.033	0.029 0.024–0.035	0.007 0.007–0.007	0.009 0.009–0.009	0.036 0.035–0.037	-
9	<i>R. rubescens</i> *	0.052 0.05–0.059	0.048 0.042–0.055	0.029 0.026–0.031	0.029 0.022–0.033	0.004 0.004–0.004	0.007 0.007–0.007	0.034 0.033–0.035	0.005 0.002–0.007

Table 2. Loadings, eigenvalues, and percentage of explained variance for first two principal components (PC's) of a Principal component analysis (PCA). This analysis was based on seven acoustic variables from the advertisement calls of 35 toads from western Ecuador (*Rhinella bella* sp. nov.), eastern Ecuador (*R. marina*) and Central America (*R. horribilis*). Additionally, one from eastern Peru was included in the analysis.

Variables	PC I	PC II
Call length	0.896	0.352
Call rise time	0.876	0.307
Notes per call	0.920	0.309
Pulses per note	-0.681	0.611
Pulse rate	-0.537	0.714
Call repetition rate	-0.641	-0.347
Dominant frequency	-0.802	0.364
Eigenvalue	4.222	1.450
% of variance explained	60.32	20.71
Cumulative %	60.32	81.03

Table 3. Descriptive statistics for call parameters of toad populations from Central America, western Ecuador and eastern Ecuador. Sample size (n), and Mean \pm SD are given. Individuals from western Ecuador correspond to *Rhinella bella sp. nov.*, individuals from eastern Ecuador correspond to *R. marina*, and individuals from Central America correspond to *R. horribilis*.

Variables	Central America ($n=5$)	Western Ecuador ($n=17$)	Eastern Ecuador ($n=12$)
Call length	6.33 \pm 1.01	1.51 \pm 0.43	5.28 \pm 4.04
Call rise time	3.75 \pm 1.86	0.94 \pm 0.26	3.09 \pm 2.19
Notes per call	83.98 \pm 11.10	18.33 \pm 5.70	81.66 \pm 61.97
Pulses per note	3.55 \pm 0.78	3.80 \pm 0.59	3.16 \pm 0.69
Pulse rate	90.57 \pm 13.87	91.31 \pm 11.70	88.92 \pm 13.66
Call repetition rate	4.41 \pm 1.61	8.57 \pm 2.40	2.96 \pm 0.86
Dominant frequency	633.02 \pm 35.28	803.05 \pm 75.7	705.52 \pm 117.24

Table 4. Loadings, eigenvalues, and percentage of explained variance for three first principal components from a principal component analysis (PCA). The analysis is based on 12 continuously varying linear and size-corrected morphometric characters of 3 toad populations and 106 specimens (see methods in the main text). Abbreviations are: SVL = Snout-vent length; TL = Tibia length; FL = Foot length; FEL = Femur length; HL = Head length; HW = Head width; IOD = Interorbital distance; IND = Internarial distance; END = Eye-nostril distance; ED = Eye diameter; TD = Tympanum diameter; THL = Thumb length; TF = Third finger length.

Variables	Code	PC I	PC II	PC III
Tibia length	TL	0.745	0.082	0.26
Foot length	FL	0.714	0.19	0.162
Femur length	FEL	0.785	0.071	0.078
Head length	HL	0.492	0.38	0.013
Head width	HW	0.762	0.185	0.12
Interorbital distance	IOD	0.044	0.829	0.053
Internarial distance	IND	0.24	0.655	-0.081
Eye-nostril distance	END	0.162	0.488	0.587
Eye diameter	ED	0.637	0.055	-0.278
Tympanum diameter	TD	0.113	-0.1	0.824
Thumb length	THL	0.455	0.402	0.166
Third finger length	TF	0.722	0.269	0.133
Eigenvalues		3.74	1.83	1.27
% of variance explained		31.12	15.23	10.54
Cumulative %		31.12	46.35	56.89

Table 5. Canonical coefficients and percentage of explained variance for canonical variables (CV) of the Canonical Variate Analysis (CVA) of 3 toad populations and 84 specimens. This analysis was based on shape variables (see main text).

Shape variables	CV I	CV II
x1	-29.5047	105.6930
y1	-137.1518	101.0467
x2	95.0278	-95.6869
y2	95.6099	-63.0279
x3	-12.6571	26.8945
y3	42.8372	-5.6094
x4	-103.9906	-19.3548
y4	-25.4385	9.6817
x5	19.2644	-18.6325
y5	-19.4825	-22.6826
x6	72.4379	17.1427
y6	-22.4482	14.6958
x7	93.5268	0.6927
y7	78.0845	9.5599
x8	-37.4333	-17.7027
y8	17.0133	-48.1208
x9	-35.4839	-36.8079
y9	2.8802	-18.1410
x10	26.1319	55.7962
y10	-19.5041	-12.9742
x11	-63.8547	15.6947
y11	11.8286	8.6709
x12	-47.9645	-10.7240

y12	8.2034	18.2051
x13	24.5003	-23.0049
y13	-32.4319	8.6958
% of variance explained	53.85	46.15
Cumulative %	53.85	100

Table 6. Loadings, eigenvalues, and percentage of explained variance for four first principal components from a principal component analysis (PCA). The analysis is based on 19 climatic variables (BIO1 – BIO19) from 98 collection localities of 3 toad populations' specimens used for the phylogenetic analysis (see Methods section).

Variables	PC I	PC II	PC III	PC IV
BIO1 - Annual Mean Temperature)	0.989	0.103	0.086	-0.045
BIO2 - Mean Diurnal Range(Mean(period max-min))	-0.056	-0.229	-0.233	0.865
BIO3 - Isothermality	0.13	0.306	0.879	-0.077
BIO4 - Temperature Seasonality (Coefficient of Variation)	-0.049	-0.228	-0.908	0.182
BIO5 - Max Temperature of Warmest Period	0.97	0.004	-0.149	0.181
BIO6 - Min Temperature of Coldest Period	0.881	0.196	0.342	-0.259
BIO7 - Temperature Annual Range	-0.121	-0.294	-0.709	0.623
BIO8 - Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	0.988	-0.003	-0.068	-0.071
BIO9 - Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter	0.949	0.215	0.192	-0.033
BIO10 - Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	0.993	0.046	-0.085	-0.019
BIO11 - Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter	0.944	0.13	0.281	-0.092
BIO12 - Annual Precipitation	0.129	0.954	0.237	-0.104
BIO13 - Precipitation of Wettest Period	0.072	0.866	-0.117	-0.316
BIO14 - Precipitation of Driest Period	0.09	0.889	0.347	0.039
BIO15 - Precipitation Seasonality (Coefficient of Variation)	0.032	-0.795	-0.471	-0.088
BIO16 - Precipitation of Wettest Quarter	0.139	0.892	-0.028	-0.308
BIO17 - Precipitation of Driest Quarter	0.076	0.894	0.355	0.026
BIO18 - Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	0.077	0.714	0.018	-0.383
BIO19 -Precipitation of Coldest Quarter	0.174	0.832	0.405	0.018
Eigenvalues	9.118	5.394	1.942	1.19

% of variance explained	34.62	33.04	16.49	8.71
Cumulative %	34.62	67.66	84.15	92.86

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Cryptic Diversity in Toads of the *Rhinella marina* species group (Anura, Bufonidae) with a subjectively beautiful new species from Western Ecuador

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Table S1. Collection localities and GenBank sequence accession numbers of the specimens used in the phylogenetic analysis.

Table S2. Information of the recordings used in the present research.

Table S3. Descriptive statistics for morphometric measurements and proportions (in percentage) of 106 toads (*Rhinella marina* species group) used in the linear morphometric analyses.

Figure S1. Configuration of landmarks for the analysis of variation in the shape of the skull

Figure S2. Axes I and II from principal components analysis (PCA) based on 13 continuously varying lineal morphological characters.

Table S4. Results of a MANOVA using scores from the first two rotated principal components (PC's; see methods) to evaluate differences among populations.

Table S5. Standardized canonical discriminant function coefficients, eigenvalues, and percentage of explained variance for canonical variables (CV I, CV II) of Canonical Variates Analysis of three toad populations.

Table S6. Coefficients of first two first principal components (relative warp [RW] axes) from a Principal component analysis (PCA) based on shape variables.

Figure S3. Axes (relative warps) I and II from principal components analysis (PCA) based on shape variables.

Table S7. Synapomorphies and other characters for *R. marina* group examined during this study.

Table S8. Descriptive statistics for morphometric measurements and proportions (in percentage) of 106 toads (*Rhinella marina* species group) separated for males and females and used in the linear morphometric analyses.

Figure S4. Phylogenetic relationships among species of the *Rhinella marina* group based on the Bayesian analysis of the 12S–16S fragment. Include sequences from “Santander, Reserva Cabildo Verde, Colombia” (see main text).

Figure S5. Phylogenetic relationships based exclusively in the nuclear DNA sequences published by Pereyra *et al.* (2021)

Table S1. Collection localities and GenBank sequence accession numbers of the specimens used in the phylogenetic analysis. New sequences generated in this study are shown in bold. Sequences with marked with (*) are 16S, the rest of the sequences correspond to the 12S + tRNAval + 16S genetic region.

Specimen	Locality	GenBank code
<i>I. alvarius</i> USMN 320001	USA: Arizona	DQ158425
<i>I. valliceps</i> USNM 534129	Mexico: Vera Cruz	DQ158493
<i>A. exsul</i> MVZ 137717	USA: California, Buckhorn Spring	DQ158450
<i>A. microscaphus</i> USNM 320147	USA: Nuevo Mexico	DQ158476
<i>A. fowleri</i> USNM 314864	USA: Mississippi, Oktibbeha, Starkville	DQ158451
<i>R. granulosa</i> AMNH A139020	Guyana: Southern Rupununi Savanna, Aishalton (on Kubabawau Creek), 150 m	DQ283332
<i>R. granulosa</i> USNM 302450	Brazil: Roraima	DQ158457
<i>R. granulosa</i> (a)	Brazil: Porto Trombetas	GU178789
<i>R. granulosa</i> (b)	Brazil: Porto Trombetas	GU178788
<i>R. crucifer</i> ZUEC-DCC3392	Brazil: Rio de Janeiro: Mage, Campo de Escoteiras, Santo Aleixo	AY680260
<i>R. crucifer</i> USNM 303015	Brazil: Sao Paulo	DQ158447
<i>R. marina</i> (a)	Costa Rica: Heredia, Chilamate	DQ415563*
<i>R. marina</i> USNM 534124	Honduras: Colon, Quebrada Machin	DQ415569*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-50638	Honduras: El Paraiso, Las Manos	DQ415568*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-50870	Guatemala: Izabal, Montañas del Mico	DQ415567*
<i>R. marina</i> KU 289772	El Salvador: Ahuachapan, El Imposible	DQ415565*
<i>R. marina</i> KU 289750	El Salvador: Ahuachapan, El Imposible	DQ158473*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-50876	Guatemala: Huehuetenango, near Nenton	DQ415566*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54870	Mexico: Guerrero, near Atoyac	DQ415561*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54871	Mexico: Veracruz, south of Cardel	DQ415559*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54868	Mexico: Sinaloa, near Cosala	DQ415562*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54869	Mexico: Guerrero, near Atoyac	DQ415560*
<i>R. marina</i> UNAM-JRM 4834	Mexico: Veracruz, near El Viejón	DQ415553*
<i>R. marina</i> UNAM-JRM 4848	Mexico: Veracruz, north of Palma Sola	DQ415549*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54878	Mexico: Veracruz, near El Viejón	DQ415558*
<i>R. marina</i> UNAM-JRM 4835	Mexico: Veracruz, near El Viejón	DQ415554*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54879	Mexico: Veracruz, near El Viejón	DQ415556*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54873	Mexico: Veracruz, near El Viejón	DQ415552*
<i>R. marina</i> UNAM-JRM 4844	Mexico: Veracruz, north of Palma Sola	DQ415550*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54881	Mexico: Veracruz, near El Viejón	DQ415555*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54875	Mexico: Veracruz, north of Palma Sola	DQ415547*
<i>R. marina</i> UNAM-JRM 4846	Mexico: Veracruz, north of Palma Sola	DQ415548*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54877	Mexico: Veracruz, near El Viejón	DQ415557*
<i>R. marina</i> UTA A-54882	Mexico: Veracruz, near El Viejón	DQ415551*
<i>R. marina</i> KU 217482	Ecuador: Loja, Vilcabamba	DQ158474
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 47445	Ecuador: Loja, San Bernabé	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 47444	Ecuador: Loja, San Bernabé	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 46001	Ecuador: Imbabura, Zona de amortiguamiento de la Reserva Cotacachi-Cayapas, near Aguas river Verdes	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 37033	Ecuador: Pichincha, Manuel Cornejo Astorga, Tandapi	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 50702	Ecuador: Manabí, San Andrés de Rocafuerte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 17965	Ecuador: Pichincha, Guayllabamba, Guayllabamba river	

<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 12039	Ecuador: Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas, Saracay Hotel	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 40424	Ecuador: Rosa Zarate, Laguna del Cube	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 39353	Ecuador: Pichincha, Tababela airport	
<i>R. marina</i> KU 202274	Ecuador: Pichincha	AY680259
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 45989	Ecuador: Imbabura, Zona de amortiguamiento de la Reserva Cotacachi-Cayapas, near Aguas Verdes river	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 40806	Ecuador: Azuay, near bridge over León river, Oña-Cuenca old road	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 28528	Ecuador: Pichincha, secondary road, near Tinalandia, riverside of Toachi river, near pipeline.	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 37088	Ecuador: Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas, Chihuilpe, Chihuilpe river	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 35433	Ecuador: Pichincha, Pedro Vicente Maldonado	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 49447	Ecuador: Manabí, Reserva Lalo Loor	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 23486	Ecuador: Guayas, trail to Cerro Más Vale	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 41327	Ecuador: Guayas, Bosque Protector Cerro Blanco	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 23324	Ecuador: Guayas, Santa Elena, road Palmas – Balsas	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 13893	Ecuador: Cañar, 300 m from Manta Real on the road to Aurora	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 24579	Ecuador: Manabí, Puerto Rico, Alándaluz	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 50701	Ecuador: Manabí, San Andrés de Rocafuerte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 50698	Ecuador: Manabí, Puerto Cayo	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 23305	Ecuador: Guayas, road El Palmar – Balsas, 20 km from El Palmar	
<i>R. arenarum</i> (a)	Uruguay: Rocha	GU178785
<i>R. arenarum</i> AR 305	Argentina	DQ158429
<i>R. arenarum</i> MACN 38639	Argentina: San Luis, ruta 20 entre Bardas Blancas y km 330	AY843573
<i>R. achavali</i> ZVCB 3801	Uruguay	GU178787
<i>R. icterica</i> AF 312	Brazil: Sao Paulo, Carapicuíba	DQ158462
<i>R. icterica</i> (a)	Brazil: Sao Paulo	GU178786
<i>R. rubescens</i> AF 388	Brazil: Minas Gerais, Santa Barbara	DQ158486
<i>R. poeppigii</i> USNM 268824	Peru: Madre Dios	DQ158481
<i>R. poeppigii</i> QCAZ 39177	Ecuador: Pastaza, Tarangaro community, Campo Villano, Bloque 10-Agip Oil	
<i>R. marina</i> MJH 3678	Peru: Puerto Inca	DQ283062
<i>R. poeppigii</i> QCAZ 40785	Ecuador: Zamora Chinchipe, Piuntza	
<i>R. poeppigii</i> MNCN/ADN6044	Bolivia: La Paz	GU178779
<i>R. marina</i> (b)	Brazil: Canaa dos Carajás	GU178782
<i>R. diptycha</i> BB 1224	Argentina: Santiago del Estero, Dto. Guasayaan, Do'a Luisa	DQ283065
<i>R. diptycha</i> KU 289057	Paraguay: San Luis de la Sierra	DQ415572*
<i>R. marina</i> (c)	Brazil: Santarém	GU178781
<i>R. marina</i> KU 205236	Peru: Cuzco	AY325994
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44399	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Chiru Isla, Banco norte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44274	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Edén, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44305	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Chiru Isla, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44084	Ecuador: Sucumbíos, Napo river, 2.5 km south from Pañacocha, Banco norte	

<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 43782	Ecuador: Orellana, 9 km south from Coca, 50 m from Napo River, Banco sur	
<i>R. diptycha</i>	Brazil: Viseu	GU178783
<i>R. diptycha</i>	Brazil: Natal	GU178784
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44524	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, San Vicente, Banco norte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 43876	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, La Primavera (El Descanso), Banco norte	
<i>R. diptycha</i> VUB 1965	Suriname	FJ882831
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44041	Ecuador: Sucumbíos, Napo river, La Selva Lodge entrance, Banco norte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44307	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Chiru Isla, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 43781	Ecuador: Orellana, 9 km south from El Coca, 50 m from Napo river, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> (e)	Brazil: Porto Trombetas	GU178780
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44306	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Chiru Isla, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 37177	Ecuador: Pastaza, Pomona, Bosque Tropical Fundación Hola Vida	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44276	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Edén, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44812	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Nuevo Rocafuerte, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 43877	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, La Primavera (El Descanso), Banco norte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44040	Ecuador: Sucumbíos, Napo river, La Selva Lodge entrance, Banco norte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44275	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Edén, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44083	Ecuador: Sucumbíos, Napo river, 2.5 km south from Pañacocha, Banco norte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 15867	Ecuador: Napo, Salado river	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 48904	Ecuador: Napo, Benavides Residence, Wildsumaco Wildlife Sanctuary, Wildsumaco Lodge	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 15413	Ecuador: Pastaza, Centro Experimental Fátima, 9 km north from Puyo	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 28402	Ecuador: Sucumbíos, Playas de Cuyabeno	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 43751	Ecuador: Orellana, 5 km south from El Coca, near Napo river, Banco Sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44015	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Áñangu, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 28022	Ecuador: Sucumbíos, Zábalo	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 32484	Ecuador: Morona Santiago, 900 m south east from Bobonaza	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44085	Ecuador: Sucumbíos, Napo river, 2.5 km south from Pañacocha, Banco norte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44663	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Santa Teresita 4 km north east from Nuevo Rocafuerte, Banco norte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44622	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Huiririma, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 48905	Ecuador: Napo, Benavides Residence, Wildsumaco Wildlife Sanctuary, Wildsumaco Lodge	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44811	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Nuevo Rocafuerte, Banco sur	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 43724	Ecuador: Orellana, El Coca, Banco norte	
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44664	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Santa Teresita 4 km north west from Nuevo Rocafuerte, Banco norte	

<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44833	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, Nuevo Rocafuerte, Banco sur
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 39418	Ecuador: Pastaza, Bataburo Lodge, south from Cononaco
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 43869	Ecuador: Orellana, Napo river, La Primavera, Banco sur
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 44014	Ecuador: Parque Nacional Yasuní, Napo river, Comunidad Añangu, Banco sur
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 41846	Ecuador: Morona Santiago: Gral. Leonidas Plaza Gutiérrez (Limón), 6,6 km north of Parque central of General Leonidas Plaza (Río Napinaza)
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 17046	Ecuador: Morona Santiago, Limón Indanza
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 41865	Ecuador: Morona Santiago, General Leonidas Plaza Gutiérrez (Limón), Napinaza river
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 32485	Ecuador: Morona Santiago, 900 m south east from Bobonaza
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 26268	Ecuador: Pastaza, 5Km from Puyo on the road to Tena
<i>R. marina</i> QCAZ 25628	Ecuador: Pastaza, Pomona, Fundación Hola Vida

Table S2. Information of the recordings used in the present research.

No. Recording	Species	Record ID	Source
1	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	2001-11-15	QCAZ, recorded by Morley Read
2	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	2001-11-15	QCAZ, recorded by Morley Read
3	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	2001-11-15	QCAZ, recorded by Morley Read
4	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	2001-11-17	QCAZ, recorded by Morley Read
5	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	2001-11-17	QCAZ, recorded by Morley Read
6	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	2001-11-17	QCAZ, recorded by Morley Read
7	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	LS110382	QCAZ, recorded by Morley Read
8	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	LS110165	EPN, Ana Almendariz
9	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	Yunguilla	EPN. Ana Almendariz
10	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	Yunguilla	EPN. Ana Almendariz
11	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	7301	KU deposited with Fonozoo. Fonoteca
12	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	7301	KU deposited with Fonozoo. Fonoteca
13	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	7818	KU deposited with Fonozoo. Fonoteca
14	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	7818	KU deposited with Fonozoo. Fonoteca
15	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	QCAZ-CC095	QCAZ. PUCE
16	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	QCAZ-CC095	QCAZ. PUCE
17	<i>Rhinella bella sp. nov</i>	QCAZ-CC095	QCAZ. PUCE
18	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	1995-7-14	QCAZ, recorded by Morley Read
19	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	1995-7-16	QCAZ, recorded by Morley Read
20	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	LS110164	EPN, Ana Almendariz
21	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	EPN. 27 de abril de 2012.
22	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	EPN. 27 de abril de 2012.
23	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	EPN. 27 de abril de 2012.
24	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	LS100373	QCAZ. PUCE
25	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	LS100375	QCAZ. PUCE
26	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	LS100375	QCAZ. PUCE
27	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	LS100377	QCAZ. PUCE
28	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	LS100374	QCAZ. PUCE
29	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	LS100374	QCAZ. PUCE
30	<i>Rhinella marina</i>	<i>Bufo marinus</i> -Tambopata	CD Tambopata
31	<i>Rhinella horribilis</i>	55248	Macaulay Library, Cornell Ornithology

32	<i>Rhinella horribilis</i>	166487	Macaulay Library, Cornell Ornithology
33	<i>Rhinella horribilis</i>	208389	Macaulay Library, Cornell Ornithology
34	<i>Rhinella horribilis</i>	193617	Macaulay Library, Cornell Ornithology
35	<i>Rhinella horribilis</i>	7147	KU deposited with Fonozoo. Fonoteca

Table S3. Descriptive statistics for morphometric measurements and proportions (in percentage) of 106 toads (*Rhinella marina* species group) used in the linear morphometric analyses. Mean \pm SD is given with range below. Abbreviations are: SVL = Snout-vent length; TL = Tibia length; FL = Foot length; FEL = Femur length; HL = Head length; HW = Head width; IOD = Interorbital distance; IND = Internarial distance; END = Eye-nostril distance; ED = Eye diameter; TD = Tympanum diameter; THL = Thumb length; TF = Third finger length. All measurements are given in mm. Toads from Central America correspond to *R. horribilis*, toads from western Ecuador correspond to *R. bella* sp. nov., and toads from eastern Ecuador correspond to “*R. marina*”.

Variables	Central America (n=20)	Western Ecuador (n=60)	Eastern Ecuador (n=26)
SVL	117.34 \pm 18.37	94.08 \pm 15.83	99.94 \pm 11.38
	81.40–148.20	65.62–140.94	79.74–133.84
TL	44.91 \pm 7.30	38.96 \pm 6.21	41.46 \pm 4.85
	30.40–58.70	27.7–58.24	33.17–56.91
FL	44.73 \pm 6.81	39.36 \pm 6.67	42.75 \pm 4.70
	31.80–55.20	27.15–62.79	33.56–53.87
FEL	45.02 \pm 8.63	39.42 \pm 6.88	43.28 \pm 5.37
	25.60–62.60	25.94–59.20	34.28–61.35
HL	36.23 \pm 5.63	30.74 \pm 4.44	32.65 \pm 3.74
	26.70–48.90	22.69–42.87	23.70–41.73
HW	44.22 \pm 7.33	37.51 \pm 6.02	41.17 \pm 4.67
	30.50–55.50	25.87–52.41	32.55–54.80
IOD	16.64 \pm 2.81	13.89 \pm 2.35	15.90 \pm 1.94
	11.40–21.50	6.24–20.01	11.93–21.19
IND	7.80 \pm 1.46	6.40 \pm 1.13	7.30 \pm 0.84
	4.60–10.10	3.38–9.32	5.82–9.36
END	7.07 \pm 1.15	6.36 \pm 0.98	6.49 \pm 0.88
	5.10–9.20	4.71–8.73	4.99–8.80
ED	11.87 \pm 1.91	10.99 \pm 1.45	11.90 \pm 1.08
	9.40–15.70	8.41–15.75	9.46–14.82
TD	4.94 \pm 0.81	4.36 \pm 0.73	4.46 \pm 0.56
	3.40–6.50	3.15–6.63	3.33–5.75
THL	13.31 \pm 1.81	11.90 \pm 2.07	12.75 \pm 1.84
	10.20–16.70	7.59–17.75	9.38–18.10
TF	12.50 \pm 1.68	13.01 \pm 2.07	14.84 \pm 1.95
	9.10–14.90	8.43–18.11	12.45–20.31
FEL/SVL	38.28 \pm 3.75	41.93 \pm 2.62	43.30 \pm 1.88
	31.45–43.65	36.29–49.13	39.39–46.87
TL/SVL	38.26 \pm 1.63	41.51 \pm 1.69	41.52 \pm 1.84
	34.28–40.93	38.24–44.61	36.05–45.03

IOD/HW	37.68 ± 1.92	37.17 ± 3.59	38.74 ± 3.44
	34.65–41.35	15.68–45.30	24.68–42.55
HW/SVL	37.66 ± 1.71	39.94 ± 1.69	41.22 ± 1.34
	34.08–40.29	35.82–43.77	39.05–43.63
TF/FL	28.05 ± 1.52	33.23 ± 3.24	34.75 ± 2.74
	25.37–30.50	25.93–39.65	30.15–39.36

Figure S1. Configuration of landmarks for the analysis of variation in the shape of the skull. The shape of the skull of each specimen was described by a set of 13 landmarks and 11 pairs of partial warps, including the uniform component (see main text).

Figure S2. Boxplot showing variation in size-corrected PC I from principal components analysis (PCA) based on 12 continuously and size-corrected varying lineal morphological characters (see methods in the main text). Individuals are classified by sex within toad populations. For eigenvectors and eigenvalues see Table 4.

Table S4. Results of a MANOVA using scores from the first three rotated principal components (PC's; see methods) to evaluate differences among of populations (i.e. eastern Ecuador, western Ecuador, Central America) only on males or females. We also performed post-hoc multiple comparison tests with the Bonferroni corrected approach.

			Multivariate Tests				
Sex			Value	<i>F</i>	Hypothesis df	Error df	<i>p</i>
Females	Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.142	2.477	3	45	.073
	Populations	Pillai's Trace	.654	7.453	6	92	.000
Males	Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.037	0.657	3	51	.582
	Populations	Pillai's Trace	.488	5.593	6	104	.000

			Tests of Between-Subjects Effects				
Sex			Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>
Females	Intercept	PC I	.129	1	.129	.235	.630
		PC II	4.686	1	4.686	6.202	.016
		PC III	.834	1	.834	.723	.399
	Populations	PC I	33.076	2	16.538	30.204	.000
		PC II	5.366	2	2.683	3.551	.037
		PC III	.407	2	.204	.176	.839
		Error	PC I	25.734	47	.548	
	PC II	35.513	47	.756			
	PC III	54.237	47	1.154			
Males	Intercept	PC I	.436	1	.436	.671	.416
		PC II	.518	1	.518	.498	.484
		PC III	.066	1	.066	.081	.778
	Populations	PC I	11.400	2	5.700	8.765	.001
		PC II	4.607	2	2.303	2.210	.120
		PC III	6.182	2	3.091	3.790	.029
		Error	PC I	34.467	53	.650	
	PC II	55.229	53	1.042			
	PC III	43.220	53	.815			

Pairwise multiple comparisons (Bonferroni)

Sex				Mean Difference	Std. Error	<i>p</i>
Females	PC I	Central America	Eastern Ecuador	-2.3079631*	.33250592	.000
			Western Ecuador	-1.6206851*	.24697920	.000
		Eastern Ecuador	Central America	2.3079631*	.33250592	.000
			Western Ecuador	.6872780	.29550394	.073
		Western Ecuador	Central America	1.6206851*	.24697920	.000
			Eastern Ecuador	-.6872780	.29550394	.073
	PC II	Central America	Eastern Ecuador	-.9647392	.39060613	.052
			Western Ecuador	-.1182516	.29013495	1.000
		Eastern Ecuador	Central America	.9647392	.39060613	.052
			Western Ecuador	.8464877	.34713863	.056
		Western Ecuador	Central America	.1182516	.29013495	1.000
			Eastern Ecuador	-.8464877	.34713863	.056
PC III	Central America	Eastern Ecuador	.0368584	.48271687	1.000	
		Western Ecuador	-.1672806	.35855309	1.000	
	Eastern Ecuador	Central America	-.0368584	.48271687	1.000	
		Western Ecuador	-.2041390	.42899908	1.000	
	Western Ecuador	Central America	.1672806	.35855309	1.000	
		Eastern Ecuador	.2041390	.42899908	1.000	
Males	PC I	Central America	Eastern Ecuador	-1.4472893*	.35920940	.001
			Western Ecuador	-.7952384	.33746202	.067
		Eastern Ecuador	Central America	1.4472893*	.35920940	.001
			Western Ecuador	.6520510*	.23897029	.026
		Western Ecuador	Central America	.7952384	.33746202	.067
			Eastern Ecuador	-.6520510*	.23897029	.026
	PC II	Central America	Eastern Ecuador	-.3101263	.45470389	1.000
			Western Ecuador	.3224707	.42717504	1.000
		Eastern Ecuador	Central America	.3101263	.45470389	1.000
			Western Ecuador	.6325970	.30249965	.124
		Western Ecuador	Central America	-.3224707	.42717504	1.000
			Eastern Ecuador	-.6325970	.30249965	.124
	PC III	Central America	Eastern Ecuador	.5431765	.40224365	.548
			Western Ecuador	-.1913489	.37789087	1.000
			Central America	-.5431765	.40224365	.548

	Eastern Ecuador	Western Ecuador	-.7345254*	.26759957	.025
	Western Ecuador	Central America	.1913489	.37789087	1.000
		Eastern Ecuador	.7345254*	.26759957	.025

Table S5. Standardized canonical discriminant function coefficients, eigenvalues, and percentage of explained variance for canonical variables (CV I, CV II) of Canonical Variates Analysis of 3 toad populations and 106 specimens. This analysis was based on 12 size-corrected continuously varying lineal morphological characters (see methods). Abbreviations are: TL = Tibia length; FL = Foot length; FEL = Femur length; HL = Head length; HW = Head width; IOD = Interorbital distance; IND = Internarial distance; END = Eye-nostril distance; ED = Eye diameter; TD = Tympanum diameter; THL = Thumb length; TF = Third finger length.

Variables	CV I	CV II
TL	-0.062	0.704
FL	-0.040	-0.010
FEL	0.117	-0.179
HL	-0.408	0.120
HW	0.567	-0.566
IOD	0.300	-0.544
IND	0.054	-0.461
END	-0.152	0.549
ED	0.375	0.270
TD	-0.152	0.072
THL	-0.560	0.006
TF	0.978	0.233
Eigenvalue	1.80	0.27
% of variance explained	86.90	13.10
Cumulative %	86.90	100

Table S6. Coefficients of the first two principal components (relative warp [RW] axes) from a Principal component analysis (PCA) based on shape variables of 84 specimens (see methods in the main text).

Shape variables	RW I	RW II
x1	0.102701	0.055277
y1	0.028933	-0.163857
x2	0.154713	0.128417
y2	0.126801	-0.10357
x3	0.283869	0.146947
y3	0.306024	0.052625
x4	-0.078018	-0.195742
y4	-0.200776	-0.154039
x5	-0.230008	-0.023626
y5	-0.415298	0.515033
x6	-0.223542	-0.39701
y6	-0.299833	0.036318
x7	-0.097952	-0.2691
y7	-0.166039	-0.189727
x8	0.072561	0.04327
y8	-0.117451	0.031577
x9	0.111692	0.035844
y9	0.051619	-0.013727
x10	0.08523	0.128461
y10	0.255215	-0.144399
x11	-0.199331	-0.169883
y11	-0.127334	0.162967
x12	0.05085	0.092802
y12	0.321476	-0.150776
x13	-0.032766	0.424342
y13	0.236662	0.121575
% of variance explained	66.95	7.65
Cumulative %	66.95	74.60

Figure S3. Axes (relative warps) I and II from principal components analysis (PCA) based on shape variables of 84 specimens (see methods in the main text). Specimens are classified by geographic region. For eigenvectors and eigenvalues see Table S5. Individuals from western Ecuador correspond to *Rhinella bella* sp. nov., individuals from eastern Ecuador correspond to *R. marina*, and individuals from Central America correspond to *R. horribilis*.

Table S7. Examined synapomorphies and other characters that new species shares with other species of *R. marina* group. We examined one out of 2 two synapomorphies and eight out of 12 characters listed in Pereyra *et al.* (2021, p. 54) from 10 specimens of the new species included in our phylogeny (QCAZ: 51478, 57032, 51799, 68814, 65726, 67265, 51423, 51308, 51846, 55040). These character states, when used in combination, help to distinguish species of the *R. marina* group from members of the other species groups of *Rhinella*.

Morphological trait (Pereyra <i>et al.</i> 2021, p. 54)	<i>Rhinella marina</i> group	<i>Rhinella bella sp.</i> <i>nov.</i>
Jagged or scalloped articulation between the medial ramus of pterygoid and parasphenoid alae	X (Synapomorphy)	Not checked
Sacral diapophyses with the anterior edge angled posteriorly to the midline axis of the vertebral column	X (Synapomorphy)	X
Preorbital crest well developed	X	X
Supraorbital crest well developed	X	X
Pretympanic crest well developed	X	X
Nasal and frontoparietal articulate along the entire margin	X	X
Occipital artery pathway completely covered with bone	X	Not checked
Medial ramus of the pterygoid fused and extending medially along approximately half the length of the parasphenoid ala	X	Not checked
Inguinal fat bodies present	X	X
Adhesive gland division after operculum fusion in embryo		Not checked
Parotid gland approximately ellipsoid, longer than wide or triangular and bulky	X	X
Tarsal fold present	X	X
Extensor digitorum longus with an insertion on the metatarsophalangeal joint of digiti IV	X	X
Eggs biserially disposed in strings	X	Not checked

Table S8. Descriptive statistics for morphometric measurements and proportions (in percentage) of 106 toads (*Rhinella marina* species group) separated for males and females and used in the linear morphometric analyses. Minimum, Maximum, Mean and Standard Deviation are given below. Abbreviations are: SVL = Snout-vent length; TL = Tibia length; FL = Foot length; FEL = Femur length; HL = Head length; HW = Head width; IOD = Interorbital distance; IND = Internarial distance; END = Eye-nostril distance; ED = Eye diameter; TD = Tympanum diameter; THL = Thumb length; TF = Third finger length. All measurements are given in mm. Toads from Central America correspond to *R. horribilis*, toads from western Ecuador correspond to *R. bella* sp. nov., and toads from eastern Ecuador correspond to *R. marina*.

Population	Sex	Variable	<i>n</i>	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Central America	Females	SVL	13	90.50	148.20	115.07	17.26
		TL	13	33.10	51.20	43.86	6.37
		FL	13	32.70	53.50	43.27	6.08
		FEL	13	31.10	54.10	43.55	6.65
		HL	13	28.60	48.90	35.92	6.04
		HW	13	33.60	52.00	43.13	6.92
		IOD	13	12.40	21.50	16.40	2.71
		IND	13	5.30	9.40	7.62	1.31
		END	13	5.30	8.80	6.87	1.02
		ED	13	9.40	15.70	11.58	2.02
		TD	13	3.40	6.00	4.81	0.76
		THL	13	10.20	14.80	12.91	1.47
		TF	13	9.80	14.40	12.20	1.47
		FEL/SVL	13	32.16	43.27	37.99	3.83
		TL/SVL	13	34.28	40.41	38.17	1.85
		IOD/HW	13	34.65	41.35	38.07	2.17
		HW/SVL	13	34.08	40.29	37.47	2.07
	TF/FL	13	25.37	30.50	28.32	1.59	
	Males	SVL	7	81.40	143.40	121.54	21.00
		TL	7	30.40	58.70	46.84	8.99
		FL	7	31.80	55.20	47.43	7.73
		FEL	7	25.60	62.60	47.74	11.58
		HL	7	26.70	42.40	36.80	5.19
		HW	7	30.50	55.50	46.24	8.20
		IOD	7	11.40	20.60	17.10	3.16
		IND	7	4.60	10.10	8.13	1.79
		END	7	5.10	9.20	7.44	1.36
ED		7	9.40	14.50	12.41	1.71	

		TD	7	3.70	6.50	5.19	0.90	
		THL	7	10.20	16.70	14.06	2.23	
		TF	7	9.10	14.90	13.04	2.02	
		FEL/SVL	7	31.45	43.65	38.80	3.85	
		TL/SVL	7	37.35	40.93	38.43	1.23	
		IOD/HW	7	35.23	38.94	36.96	1.15	
		HW/SVL	7	37.17	38.87	38.02	0.69	
		TF/FL	7	26.45	30.22	27.57	1.36	
Eastern Ecuador	Females	SVL	8	91.76	133.84	107.64	12.72	
		TL	8	39.01	56.91	44.81	5.34	
		FL	8	40.57	53.87	46.16	5.09	
		FEL	8	39.20	61.35	47.01	6.50	
		HL	8	31.19	41.73	35.26	3.51	
		HW	8	37.91	54.80	44.25	5.37	
		IOD	8	16.13	21.19	17.68	1.65	
		IND	8	6.75	9.36	7.88	0.87	
		END	8	5.24	8.80	7.10	1.07	
		ED	8	10.97	14.82	12.50	1.26	
		TD	8	3.90	5.75	4.64	0.63	
		THL	8	11.86	18.10	14.66	1.79	
		TF	8	12.45	20.31	16.66	2.20	
		FEL/SVL	8	41.99	45.84	43.61	1.23	
	TL/SVL	8	39.40	45.03	41.67	1.73		
	IOD/HW	8	38.16	42.55	40.10	1.75		
	HW/SVL	8	39.26	42.18	41.10	1.12		
	TF/FL	8	30.17	39.36	36.11	3.17		
		Males	SVL	18	79.74	111.56	96.52	9.14
			TL	18	33.17	45.83	39.98	3.90
			FL	18	33.56	45.56	41.24	3.73
			FEL	18	34.28	47.48	41.62	3.94
			HL	18	23.70	37.82	31.50	3.30
			HW	18	32.55	48.34	39.81	3.72
			IOD	18	11.93	17.34	15.11	1.50
			IND	18	5.82	8.42	7.06	0.72
			END	18	4.99	7.77	6.23	0.67
			ED	18	9.46	12.89	11.64	0.91
	TD		18	3.33	5.55	4.38	0.53	
	THL		18	9.38	13.69	11.91	1.10	
	TF		18	12.78	16.62	14.03	1.15	
	FEL/SVL		18	39.39	46.87	43.17	2.13	
	TL/SVL	18	36.05	43.38	41.45	1.94		

		IOD/HW	18	24.68	41.84	38.14	3.86	
		HW/SVL	18	39.05	43.63	41.28	1.45	
		TF/FL	17	30.15	38.08	34.13	2.45	
Western Ecuador	Females	SVL	29	84.22	140.94	102.16	13.75	
		TL	29	32.84	58.24	41.81	5.52	
		FL	29	33.84	62.79	42.66	6.35	
		FEL	29	34.02	59.20	42.60	6.05	
		HL	29	28.39	42.87	33.10	3.29	
		HW	29	32.70	52.41	40.40	4.79	
		IOD	29	12.50	20.01	15.14	1.66	
		IND	29	3.38	9.32	6.91	1.05	
		END	29	5.44	8.73	6.80	0.82	
		ED	29	10.73	15.75	11.81	1.17	
		TD	29	3.42	6.20	4.50	0.67	
		THL	29	9.79	17.75	13.34	1.42	
		TF	29	11.61	18.11	14.10	1.50	
		FEL/SVL	29	36.29	48.24	41.74	2.62	
		TL/SVL	29	38.24	44.61	40.98	1.78	
		IOD/HW	29	33.72	42.14	37.57	2.15	
		HW/SVL	29	35.82	42.63	39.64	1.58	
		TF/FL	29	25.93	39.61	33.37	3.50	
			Males	SVL	31	65.62	118.37	86.51
			TL	31	27.70	50.59	36.30	5.68
		FL	31	27.15	49.44	36.28	5.43	
		FEL	31	25.94	50.91	36.45	6.33	
		HL	31	22.69	38.42	28.52	4.26	
		HW	31	25.87	47.41	34.80	5.85	
		IOD	31	6.24	18.73	12.72	2.32	
		IND	31	4.13	8.29	5.92	1.00	
		END	31	4.71	7.80	5.96	0.97	
		ED	31	8.41	12.94	10.24	1.28	
		TD	31	3.15	6.63	4.24	0.78	
		THL	31	7.59	14.48	10.56	1.64	
		TF	31	8.43	16.86	11.99	2.03	
		FEL/SVL	31	36.71	49.13	42.11	2.65	
		TL/SVL	31	38.53	44.39	42.01	1.46	
		IOD/HW	31	15.68	45.30	36.80	4.55	
		HW/SVL	31	36.16	43.77	40.22	1.76	
		TF/FL	31	26.27	39.65	33.09	3.03	

Figure S4. Phylogenetic relationships among species of the *Rhinella marina* group based on the Bayesian analysis of the 12S–16S fragment. Numbers above the branches are Bayesian posterior probability values in percentages. Posterior probabilities higher than 90% are marked with an asterisk (*). Clade A corresponds to *R. horribilis*, Clade B to ***R. bella sp. nov.***, Clades D most probably to *R. poeppigii* (see Discussion section) and clade E to *R. marina*. The sequences from “Santander, Reserva Cabildo Verde, Colombia” are highlighted in red. These sequences were obtained from literature (Guarnizo *et al.*, 2015).

Figure S5. Phylogenetic relationships based exclusively in the nuclear DNA sequences published by Pereyra *et al.* (2021). Sequences highlighted in red corresponds to *R. bella* sp. nov. according to our main phylogeny in the main text (the complete tree is not shown).

